

EDUCASH

A Capstone Project

Presented to the Faculty of the
College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

by

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The capstone project entitled:

EDUCASH

submitted by Von Andrei G. Awacay, Jhon Patrick B. Perez, and Jonh Lorence G. Reyes
have been examined and are recommended for Oral Defense.

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The Faculty of College of Information Technology of the University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos accepts the capstone project entitled:

EDUCASH

submitted by Von Andrei G. Awacay, Jhon Patrick B. Perez, and Jonh Lorence G. Reyes in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology.

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EduCash

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ABSTRACT

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 promotes inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Despite ongoing efforts, many college students in Bacolod City continue to experience financial hardship that limits access to higher education and academic continuity. In response, EduCash was developed as a web based financial assistance platform that connects underprivileged yet academically qualified students with donors, non-government organizations, and scholarship agencies. The system integrates scholarship matching, document verification, donor portals, and secure financial transaction modules supported by multiple digital payment gateways. Student eligibility is assessed through academic credentials and verification processes, while scholarship agencies manage postings and fund distribution through predefined calculation methods. The application also allows students to track the status of their scholarship applications in real time. Donors and scholarship agencies monitor fund allocations and verify transactions securely. By integrating these features, EduCash ensures a reliable experience.

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY CONCEPTS

• Web-Based Application Development • Model-View-Controller (MVC) Architecture • Document Verification and Data Validation.

KEYWORDS

Underprivileged College Students, Data Analytics, Scholarship Matching and Postings, Calculations.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Education is a universal and transformative human right that boosts development and empowers individual and community growth. Such an instrument is, so far, one of the greatest enablers in overcoming this cycle of poverty, as it addresses systemic inequalities at several levels. Education equips people with knowledge and skills that play an extremely important role in improving health outcomes, supporting equal gender relations, promoting peaceful coexistence, and sustaining a sustainable social order. Education benefits are deep and broad. Economically, it provides tremendous and steady returns: higher incomes, better jobs, and the capacity to work in meaningful ways within the community. Socially, education is the foundation of equity, inclusion, and bridging gaps between groups, giving everyone, regardless of walk of life, equal opportunities to succeed [WWW01]. United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), Quality Education [WWW02], emphasizes this to ensure equitable and inclusive quality education for everyone.

Bacolod City is home to several colleges and universities. Bacolod City is often called the "City of Smiles" and is now booming as a center of higher education in the Western Visayas region of the Philippines. The city has numerous colleges and universities that offer diverse academic opportunities to students across the region. Such institutions foster an atmosphere in which students strive to achieve excellence in the fields of science and technology, the arts, and the social sciences. Students at Bacolod City College are committed to achieving academic success, thereby enabling them to attain vital individual and career goals. However, many students enrolled in colleges in Bacolod City still face significant financial constraints that limit their ability to pursue a collegiate education. Tuition and regular expenses, along with limited funds, seriously burden students and their families. Affected families are the most vulnerable to low-income statuses. Thus, there is a critical need for freely available scholarships, grants, and other financial

aid to help overcome the economic constraints that hinder the scholarly and professional goals of students.

EduCash, a web-based application, aims to address the obstacles college students in Bacolod City face. By providing an application for them that connects them with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and other individuals eager to provide financial support, EduCash enables them to donate funds through registered scholarship agencies in the application. These funds are disbursed to students later by closing the gap between donors and recipients. The inspiration for developing this application is to encourage a culture of eagerness and community support, aligned with the mission for equitable education under SDG 4.

1.1 Project Scope

EduCash is a web-based application that aims to financially assist college students who are underprivileged but qualified to benefit from the program, through donations from NGOs and other individuals. EduCash only serves college students currently academically based in Bacolod City. The following sections provide the discussion that defines the project scope and identifies the project requirements.

2 METHODOLOGY

The EduCash system focuses on creating an accessible, efficient web-based platform that enables real-time interaction among underprivileged students, donors, and scholarship agencies. The system uses a centralized web application developed with PHP and MySQL, following the Model-View-Controller architecture, to manage user accounts, scholarship matching, document verification, and financial transactions. Core modules continuously process user-submitted data, including academic records, eligibility requirements, and donation information, ensuring accurate evaluations and reliable system operations. This approach supports dependable data handling, secure transactions, and ease of use, particularly for users with limited technical resources. The web application serves as the primary interface, featuring intuitive dashboards and visual representations of data in tables, graphs, and charts. Users monitor scholarship matches, donation summaries, and application statuses, while administrators track system performance and participation trends. The platform also supports data logging and report export for documentation and analysis. In addition, EduCash includes informational sections that guide scholarship procedures, eligibility requirements, and financial assistance processes.

2.1 Design and Implementation Controls

In implementing this web-based application, there are no systems capable of performing any act without boundaries. In systems development, constraints and

difficulties are commonly encountered, such as in user interface design. This section discusses the areas of concern in the development of the application.

2.2 Operating Environment

This web-based application solicits funds from donors, specifically the NGO and other individuals eager to support this cause, enabling students to earn financial support based on their academic performance to ensure increased motivation and engagement in user studies. To provide a successful development phase, it is essential to identify the hardware and software specifications that support these tools. The hardware requirements for development have been carefully selected to ensure optimal performance throughout the project and minimize wasted time. Perhaps the most distinguished member of this list is the AMD Ryzen 5 [AR2007], one of the fastest processors available today, known for its speed and multitasking potential. Such a CPU offers immense power and efficiency for functions such as code compilation, demand management algorithms, and debug tests, all while running the development workstation in the SAF environment. Its multi-core architecture therefore provides the much-needed capability to meet performance demands in resource-intensive applications, such as backend processes and online media applications, without consuming additional resources, thereby promoting productivity by reducing lag. To complement the process power, 8 GB of DDR4 RAM is included, providing a reliable amount of memory. This means developers are able to open multiple applications, such as IDEs, version control systems, virtual machines, and browsers for testing, simultaneously with enjoyable performance. The project team effortlessly drift into the code to be debugged and continue testing. Secondary storage ranging from 256 GB to 512 GB SSD, providing a broader range of responsiveness. An SSD reduces the time it takes to start up files and applications, thus booting faster, reading and writing faster, and ultimately maximizing the user experience. More useful in the phase of compilation and deployment since data and resource access are needed with extraordinary rapidity there. The paper illustrates the key software tools used to build the application and the collaboration processes involved.

Integrated Environment: Visual Studio Code [VS2021] provides an Integrated IDE with highly flexible, lightweight development and bug-fixing functionality. Git/GitHub [GIT2005] is used for version control to keep project files secure and enable team collaboration. PowerShell acts as an automation and system maintenance scripting terminal for the project team. For frontend development, the project team intends to use Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML), Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), and Bootstrap 5 alongside JavaScript for an interactive user interface. PHP is used for backend development. MySQL is used for database management in the backend. The application is

deployed on a Windows 10 or higher workstation. Three communication platforms are used within the project team: Microsoft Teams, Discord, and Google. These modes enable complete interaction among project team members, sensitive planning, real-time coordination, and documentation. Table 1 outlines the requirements for developing and implementing this project.

Component	Software Tool
Integrated Development Environment (IDE)	Visual Code Studio
Version Control	Git/GitHub
Terminals	Power shell
Frontend Development	Hypertext Markup Language (HTML)/ Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)/ JavaScript
Backend Development	PHP, MySQL
Operating System	Windows 10/11
Communication Applications	Microsoft Teams/ Discord
Collaboration Applications	Google Docs
Search Engine	Google Chrome
Prototyping	Figma
Frameworks and Libraries	BOOTSTRAP 5, jQuery
Engines	Tesseract OCR, PHP Mailer

Table 1. Software Recommendations.

2.3 Features and Functionalities

The five general features of the system are illustrated in Figure 1, namely Allowance Distribution, Donor Portal, Scholarship Match, Data Analytics, and Document Verification. Based on the components presented, which together form the application performance process, the project team planned and reviewed the specification to ensure the successful development and launch of the application. Each feature is designed to ensure a smooth transaction in the application. The project team aims to seamlessly integrate these features to provide a user-friendly, efficient application for donors and recipients. The development process involves a detailed plan and repeated tests to ensure that each feature effectively meets user needs. As shown in the sections that follow and in subsequent sections of this chapter, discuss the assumptions and dependencies, and comprehensively understand and analyze the project that facilitated its development. These features serve as the foundation of the overall functionality and operational flow of the systems. The integration of these components ensures that processes within the application are coordinated and properly managed. These features operate under specific assumptions and dependencies, where accurate data input, successful document verification, and proper system integration are required to ensure

reliable scholarship matching, transparent donor transactions, and efficient allowance distribution.

Figure 1: EduCash General Features.

As shown in Figure 1, the Donor Portal feature provided donors a way to contribute monetarily to support the goals of the project through payment integrations of the bank system, as one-time or repeated donors to the scholarship agencies. Donors also donate through payment gateways integrated into the application, such as PayPal, GCash, and Maya. Individual donors choose to remain anonymous for those who value privacy and do not want to be acknowledged. This feature also provides donors with proof of their donation through an acknowledgement receipt generated by the application. The acknowledgement receipt includes the purpose of the transaction of the user, which is to donate. The receipt provides the donor with a view of the user transaction, including the amount of the user donation, the agency to which the donor donated, and the time and date of the transaction. The Scholarship Matching feature provided students with faster, smoother access to scholarships that cater to students academically based in Bacolod City. Users provide the necessary information to apply for a scholarship, including their credentials and school performance. After which, the system provides them with the scholarship agency to which their credentials are matched. This feature also helps scholarship agencies find qualified students who meet user criteria and user-specific requirements. The requirements set by the scholarship agencies in the application students fill out serve only as a screening process, not as a direct path to being considered an official applicant for the user program. Only the approval for further transactions is sent to students as a notification. The data analytics feature displayed on a dashboard includes the total amount of donations collected, the total number of applicants, and the total number of NGO donors, represented in a bar graph, along with a pie chart showing the percentage of individual and anonymous donors. This feature serves as a significant element for the evaluation of the performance of the application. Generation of comprehensive reports to provide users with a valuable awareness of the operation and impact of the application. Specifically, the application provides an analysis and displays key metrics that are discussed further in this section of the paper. In the Allowance Distribution feature, the students are able to claim

financial aid calculated by the application via payment gateways integrated into the application.

The distribution is scheduled on a specific month each semester, and each time before the distribution, students must submit their academic performance reports. Students must maintain their academic performance to meet the eligibility criteria and avoid being classified as dropped by the scholarship agency. When the general average falls below the criteria set by the scholarship agency, this allows them to disqualify the applicant from availing the provisions from the scholarship agencies, and the student is not able to match with the scholarship agency for the next period of disbursement until the criteria are met again. Lastly, the Document Verification feature arguably becomes one of the great features incorporated into the application to sustain the originality and authenticity of the submission of the users. It is the defense that protects the integrity of the application against schemes such as fraudulent submissions and misrepresentation. This set of operations protects the integrity of the identity of the applicants and other assertions in more thorough verification to prove that they are an ethically and legitimately acceptable candidate for the benefited service. It validates uploads from supported documents, academic records, financial statements, and identity proofs through stringent loopholes verification. The system further minimizes errors by checking every document against a reliable database while providing robust security services to detect attempts at crashes and forgeries.

2.4 Interfaces and Interactions

The user interfaces of the EduCash application are the gateway through which donors, students, and scholarship agencies, together with the admin, interact with one another. The user interfaces encompass the interactive and visual elements that enable seamless access to features and navigation. This section of the chapter explores the principles, usability, and layout that ensure an intuitive and engaging user experience. EduCash provided a color-coded interface depending on the user types to prevent confusion, and by consolidating the background color to identify different account types, such as donors, scholarship agencies, and students.

As shown in Figure 2, when the donor clicks on the donate section on the side navigation bar, the donor is then redirected to the form where the donate feature is accessible, using the form to fill out. The donors are able to search by filling out the location of the scholarship agency and the minimum average requirement required in the scholarship agency and clicking on the search button. Below the form is the list of the verified scholarship agencies. As shown in previous figure, the interface displays the profile picture and the name of the scholarship agency that are verified by the admin, and criteria are set for matching. This design ensures easy identification of verified

scholarship agencies and supports informed and transparent donation decisions.

Figure 2. Donor Portal.

When the user selects the Reports button from the sidebar section, the system redirects the user to a dedicated dashboard page that consolidates all analytical graphs and reports generated by the application. This interface serves as a centralized monitoring tool for administrators and authorized users, allowing them to assess system performance and participation trends at a glance. The first visual component displayed on the dashboard is a pie chart that illustrates the distribution of donor types within the system. This chart presents the proportional representation of contributors, including non-government organizations, anonymous donors, government agencies, private companies, and specific individual donors. By categorizing donor participation, the chart highlights the diversity of support sources that willingly contribute to assisting underprivileged and deserving students. The second component is a line chart that displays the cumulative number of student beneficiaries added to the system on a monthly basis. This visualization allows users to observe growth patterns in student participation over time, identify periods of increased enrollment, and assess the overall reach of the platform. Lastly, the dashboard includes a bar graph showing the total donations collected each month. This graph provides a clear comparison of donation trends over time, enabling users to evaluate fundraising performance, identify peak donation periods, and support data-driven decision-making.

Overall, the reports and dashboard interface enhances transparency and supports informed decision-making by presenting key system metrics in a clear and accessible visual format, enabling administrators to monitor system performance, track participation and donation trends, identify patterns over time, and assess the overall impact and effectiveness of the EduCash platform in achieving its objectives. This visualization also aids in planning, improving resource allocation, and ensuring support reaches students who need it most. As shown in Figure 3, the reports and dashboard interface present a structured and visually organized

screen layout designed to provide users with clear and meaningful insights into the system data

Figure 3. Data Analytics Reports.

Upon clicking the scholarship section in the side navigation bar, the student is redirected to a page where scholarships that match their credentials are displayed. As shown in Figure 4, the scholarship agencies matched the qualifications and living conditions of the students. The interface also displays the application deadline and the scholarship agency profile photo.

Figure 4. Scholarship Matching.

As shown in Figure 5, Once a student is registered and has logged in to an existing student account, the student is then redirected to the form where necessary documents and files are uploaded and validated by the application. The students are required to upload the certificate of enrolment, validated school ID, and the certified true copy of grades for the application to verify that the user is currently enrolled. To verify that the student is in need or underprivileged when it comes to the financial aspect, some documents are required to be submitted, which include the certificate of indigency and the proof of income of the parents of the student. The application aims only to support students who are underprivileged but deserving and have commendable academic performance. The uploaded documents are carefully reviewed and validated by the application to ensure accuracy and eligibility before proceeding with the scholarship matching process. The validation supports the application in identifying eligible students based on the required documents. This process ensures

that only eligible students are considered, maintaining fairness and integrity in scholarship allocation.

Figure 5. Document Verification.

After selecting a calculation method, scholarship agencies disburse funds to students, with guidance on the amount and number of students. As shown in Figure 6, the total amount of donations and the total number of students are visible. A button with a bank icon is visible as an action that, when clicked, redirects the page to the payment gateways interface.

Figure 6. Allowance Distribution.

3 PERFORMANCE TESTING AND EVALUATION

This section of the paper in Table 2, discusses how the EduCash application effectively and efficiently implemented its functionalities and features. In evaluating the performance of the application, many measures were used and implemented to improve its performance, which helped the project team to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the application to perform more efficiently. The software quality attributes were used to evaluate the features of the

application. EduCash had four major functionalities, such as Account Creation and Management, Scholarship Matching and Postings, Financial Transactions, and Data Analytics. The software quality model, ISO 25010 [ISO25], was used as a reference to evaluate the system features of the EduCash application. Five leading quality attributes, such as Security, Usability, Reliability, Performance Efficiency, and Maintainability, were used to examine and evaluate the features of the application. The project team evaluated the authentication process, which included the login and registration for security, to ensure that the application safely keeps the information of the users. The security attribute included the following criteria: confidentiality, Integrity, Accountability, and Authenticity. As for the Scholarship Matching, the quality attribute was used to evaluate its performance in matching student profiles to scholarship agencies. As for the Financial Transactions module, the primary quality attribute is Security, specifically integrity, based on the ISO/IEC 25010 model. Integrity ensures that all donation and scholarship fund transactions are processed and stored without unauthorized alteration, duplication, or loss. This guarantees the accuracy and trustworthiness of financial records, which are essential for maintaining donor confidence and ensuring the fair distribution of scholarship funds. For the Data Analytics module of EduCash, the primary quality attribute is accuracy, under the Functional Suitability category of ISO/IEC 25010. Accuracy ensures that the analytical output, such as applicant statistics, donor contributions, scholarship demand, and matching outcomes, correctly represent the underlying system data. This guarantees trustworthy insights for students, agencies, and administrators, enabling reliable decision-making based on accurate quantitative results.

System Features	Software Quality Attributes and Models	Software Quality Criteria	Mean Score	Feature Mean Score
Account Creation and Management	Security	Integrity	50%	62.5%
		Confidentiality	75%	
		Authenticity	62.5%	
Scholarship Matching and Postings	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	91.7%
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	100%	
Financial Transactions	Security	Integrity	83%	83.23%
		Confidentiality	100%	
		Authenticity	66.7%	
Calculations	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	80.6
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	66.7%	

Table 2. Summary of Features, Attributes, and Results

Table 3 presents the percentage ranges and their corresponding interpretations for the feature mean scores. It helps explain the derived quality scores and enables the project team to assess the performance of the system features based on its attributes. A percentage range of 84.1%-100% is marked as the highest rate a

feature is able to receive, while having a 36% as the lowest rate.

Mean Score	Percentage range	Remarks
4.21-5.00	84.1% – 100%	Very Good
3.41-4.20	68.1% – 84.0%	Good
2.61-3.40	52.1% – 68.0%	Average
1.81-2.60	36.1% – 52.0%	Poor
1.00-1.80	20.0% – 36.0%	Very Poor

Table 3. Mean Score Interpretation.

3.1 Integrity

The software quality attribute that ensures computer programs and data are protected from unauthorized access or modification, maintaining accuracy, consistency, and trustworthiness, is integrity. Assessed using Formula 1, the mean integrity score was calculated as the number of resolved requirements divided by the total number of requirements. This provides a quantitative measure of the ability of the system to maintain its intended state in the face of potential threats or errors.

$$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}}$$

Formula 1. Integrity Formula.

3.2 Confidentiality

The software quality attribute that ensures that data are accessible only to authorized users, protecting sensitive information from unauthorized access, modification, or exploitation, is confidentiality. Assessed using Formula 2, the evaluation of confidentiality was quantified by dividing the number of resolved confidentiality requirements by the total number of requirements. This provides a clear measure of how effectively the system met its security objectives.

$$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 2. Confidentiality Formula.

3.3 Authenticity

The software quality attribute that refers to the degree to which a user identity is verified as truly belonging to the individual claiming it is authenticity. Assessed using Formula 3, the authenticity metric was calculated by dividing the number of resolved functions by the total number of requirements. This provides a quantitative measure of how effectively the system verifies and validates user identities.

$$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 3. Authenticity Formula.

3.4 Correctness

The software quality attribute that refers to the degree to which a system produces accurate and reliable results, as demonstrated in Formula 4. The correctness metric was calculated by dividing the number of successfully implemented functions by the total number of functions. This provides a quantitative measure of how effectively the system meets its functional requirements.

$$CR = \frac{\text{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 4. Correctness Formula.

3.5 Completeness

The software quality attribute that reflects the degree to which a system functions satisfy all user goals and specified tasks. Assessed using Formula 5, the mean completeness score was calculated as the number of requirements met divided by the total number of requirements. This provides a quantitative measure of how thoroughly the system fulfills its intended purpose.

$$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 5. Completeness Formula.

3.6 Consistency

The software quality attribute that reflects the degree to which system functions behave uniformly and reliably across all operations. Assessed using Formula 6, the consistency mean score was calculated by dividing the number of consistent functions by the total number of specified functions and multiplying the result by 100. This provides a quantitative measure of the system reliability and predictability.

$$CS = \frac{\text{number of consistent functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 6. Consistency Formula.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this capstone provides a summary of the solutions developed to address the financial

challenges faced by underprivileged yet academically qualified college students in Bacolod City through the EduCash application. This section consolidates the results obtained during the development and evaluation phases and emphasizes the overall functionality of the system and effectiveness. Its objective is to present a clear and comprehensive overview of the project findings and outcomes, demonstrating the effectiveness of the application in delivering transparent financial assistance, scholarship matching, and user support.

4.1. Conclusion

EduCash effectively achieves the objectives outlined in its design and implementation by providing a comprehensive web-based platform that supports underprivileged yet academically qualified college students in Bacolod City. The system integrates secure financial processes, scholarship management, and user-friendly interfaces to promote transparency and accessibility. Overall, the application demonstrates its effectiveness as a reliable solution for educational financial assistance. A web-based application was developed to connect students, donors, and scholarship agencies. The system was designed to ensure secure user authentication, efficient data handling, and role-based access for different user types. The donor portal enables various donors to provide financial support through secure and integrated payment gateways. Transaction records and generated receipts enhance transparency and allow donors to track their contributions. The system implements scholarship matching by evaluating academic performance and eligibility requirements of the student defined by scholarship agencies. It supports structured allowance distribution using predefined calculation methods to ensure fair allocation of funds. The system provides dashboards that visualize donation trends, applicant statistics, and scholarship distributions using graphs and charts. These visual tools support monitoring and evaluation of system performance by authorized users. The system validates academic, financial, and identity records to maintain system integrity and prevent fraudulent submissions. The verification process ensures that only qualified and legitimate applicants are considered for financial assistance.

In conclusion, EduCash presents a system that incorporates secure financial transactions, scholarship matching, data analytics, and document verification. These core features are aligned with the design objective of the project. Together, they ensure that the system effectively supports transparent and reliable scholarship management.

4.2 Recommendations

A good way to improve EduCash efficiency and credibility is to implement a system-generated receipt feature that automatically validates transactions and produces standardized digital receipts. By extracting and verifying transaction details from payment

gateways and generating official receipts with unique identifiers and QR codes. The system reduces manual processing, prevent fraudulent submissions, and strengthen financial transparency while improving donor satisfaction.

Another important enhancement is the full integration of payment gateways such as GCash, PayPal, and Maya directly into the EduCash platform. By embedding these gateways through official APIs, the system enables real-time transaction confirmation, automated recording, and immediate receipt generation. This results in a faster and more seamless donation experience while eliminating errors caused by manual receipt uploads and delayed verification.

Lastly, enforcing a one student, one scholarship agency policy ensures fair and equitable distribution of financial aid across beneficiaries. By limiting students to a single active scholarship at a time, the system prevents resource hoarding, simplifies fund tracking, and promotes ethical allocation of support. This policy also maximizes the platform's overall social impact by assisting a greater number of deserving students.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Education is a universal and transformative human right that boosts development and empowers individual and community growth. Such an instrument is, so far, one of the most significant enablers for overcoming this cycle of poverty, as it addresses systemic inequalities at multiple levels. Education equips people with knowledge and skills that play a vital role in improving health outcomes, supporting equal gender relations, promoting peaceful coexistence, and sustaining a sustainable social order. Education benefits are deep and broad. Economically, it provides tremendous and steady returns: higher incomes, better jobs, and the capacity to work in meaningful ways within the community. Socially, education is the foundation of equity, inclusion, and bridging gaps between groups, giving everyone, regardless of walk of life, equal opportunities to succeed [WB2024]. United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), Quality Education [SDGQE4], emphasizes this to ensure equitable and inclusive quality education for everyone.

Bacolod City is home to several colleges and universities. Bacolod City is often called the "City of Smiles" and is now booming as a center of higher education in the Western Visayas region of the Philippines. The city has numerous colleges and universities that offer diverse academic opportunities to students across the region. Such institutions foster an atmosphere in which students strive for excellence in science and technology, the arts, and the social sciences. Students at Bacolod City College. The researchers aim to promote inclusive and equitable access to education. The researchers are committed to achieving academic success, thereby enabling to attain vital individual and career goals.

However, many students enrolled in colleges in Bacolod City still face significant financial constraints that limit their ability to pursue a collegiate education. Tuition and regular expenses, along with limited funds, seriously burden students and their families. Affected families are the most vulnerable to low-income statuses. Thus, there is a critical need for freely available scholarships, grants, and other financial aid to help overcome the economic constraints that hinder the scholarly and professional goals of eager students.

EduCash, a web-based application, aims to address the obstacles college students in Bacolod City face. By providing an application for them that connects them with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and other individuals eager to provide financial support, EduCash enables them to donate funds through registered scholarship agencies in the application. These funds are disbursed to students later by closing the gap between donors and recipients. The inspiration for developing this application is to encourage a culture of eagerness and community support, aligned with the mission for equitable education under SDG.

1.1 Purpose

With funds from various donors and efficient transactions with scholarship agencies, the project aims to provide financial support to underprivileged, yet qualified college students based in Bacolod City. In this section of the chapter, the project team has formulated three purposes for the EduCash project that ultimately aim to bridge the gap between financial needs and educational opportunities. Purpose such as an application that connects recipients to donors, fast scholarship matching, and provision of calculations for

the disbursement of the money to the college students who are based in Bacolod City. The following sections discuss the three purposes of the application.

1.1.1 Application for Donors and Recipients

The application comprises a number of actors, including individual donors, private and government agencies, and several NGO and scholarship agencies, who are eager to support and contribute to the good cause the application seeks to embody. The main objective of the application is to provide a centralized space for donors to offer basic financial assistance to needy students who show great promise and deserve opportunities for academic success. In contrast, students are still academically based in Bacolod City. To achieve this objective, the application set up criteria and conditions that students must meet to be qualified and have access to the system, including maintaining satisfactory grades and demonstrating other forms of commendable academic performance. Conditions are monitored each semester to ensure that students remain qualified to receive financial support from donors and remain eligible for the application.

1.1.2 Cash Disbursements

With the support of monetary donations from NGOs and individual donors eager to support the application, EduCash aims to provide a calculated cash disbursement to each scholarship agency. This disbursement serves as a guideline for how the agencies allocate the donations over a specified period to student recipients. Such an approach promoted systematic fund distribution, enhanced financial oversight, and ensured congruence with the temporal and economic needs of the beneficiaries.

1.1.3 Scholarship Matching

The application is linked to scholarship agencies and college students who are academically based in Bacolod City. The application provides scholarship agencies with access, allowing users to publish opportunities and directly interact with applicants, and serves as the primary recipient of funds to be disbursed to students. As for the students, the purpose is to provide them with quick inquiries to scholarship agencies and applications. Students efficiently match with scholarship agencies that match user credentials and academic performance by filtering criteria. Another purpose of this is to ensure that qualified students quickly find a scholarship that suits them.

1.2 Technical Review of Related Systems

EduCash is a donation application specifically designed to aid underprivileged and qualified college students who are academically based in Bacolod City. Unlike other general donation systems like Give Lively [GL2015], Donorbox [DB2014], and GoFundMe [GM2010], which cater to a wide range of purposes, the EduCash application focuses exclusively on educational support through monetary donations. The application uses eligibility-based selection to ensure that only students who meet the financial aid and specific academic requirements are considered. This appends a component of accountability and transparency that is often missing in larger fundraising applications. Moreover, EduCash permits closer engagement between donors, such as NGO, and individual or anonymous donors, and recipients, who are the underprivileged college

students academically based in Bacolod City, offering a unique opportunity for donors to track the progress of the students the Donor supports. The systems mentioned above existed and influenced the project, including the functions that enabled the systems to act as applications between donors and recipients. However, there are differences between EduCash and these systems. Illustrated in Table 1 are the criteria to identify the divergences between related systems and the discussion of each system mentioned.

Application/ Criteria	Give Lively	Donorbox	GoFundMe	EduCash
Payment Gateways	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PayPal ○ All major Credit Cards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Google Pay ○ Apple Pay ○ Paypal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ All Major Credit Card ○ PayPal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Paypal ○ GCash ○ Maya
Data Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Non-profit EIN ○ Email Verification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Automated Receipts ○ Endorsements and Certifications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identity Verification ○ Fraud Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Email Verification ○ Document Verification
Security Measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SSL ○ Database Encryption ○ PCI Compliance ○ Underpinned by industry leading partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fraud Detection and monitoring tokenization ○ PCI Compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fraud Detection ○ Data Encryption ○ PCI Compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Secured Remittance ○ User-authentication ○ Data Protection
Donor Portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create, edit, or update account ○ Donation History ○ List of Repeated Donors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Receipts ○ Manage repeated donations ○ Profile Information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create Profile ○ Track Donations ○ Access campaign updates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Donor Profiles ○ Agency Profiles

Table 1. Comparative Matrix of Related Systems.

1.2.1 Payment Gateway

This criterion referred to the available methods donors use to process financial donations, allowing users to donate to different causes or organizations. The systems Give Lively, Donorbox, and GoFundMe each use their own set of payment methods to ensure donors contribute securely and support user-preferred transaction methods. Give Lively allows donors to donate via PayPal [PP2002], reducing the difficulty for people who already have PayPal accounts and eliminating the need to re-enter payment information. Donors also use credit or debit cards. Give Lively offers transparency with a donation receipt that is automatically sent to the email address of the Donor. In Addition, Give Lively also accepts all major credit cards through user payment gateways.

On the other hand, Donorbox offers a larger array of payment methods than Give Lively. Donorbox supports modern payment methods such as Apple Pay [AP2014] and Google Pay [GP2018], providing a wide range of options for donors who prefer mobile or digital wallets, which are increasingly popular for their user-friendly and security features. In addition, Donorbox allows donors to donate via PayPal through all major credit cards in users payment gateways.

As for EduCash, the application seamlessly integrates multiple payment gateways, including PayPal, Maya [MY1998], and GCash [CA2012], as well as bank payment integrations via a bank Application Programming Interface (API). This multifaceted payment system allows donors to easily contribute financially to qualified students and offers them a range of convenient, secure payment options. With these diverse channels, EduCash ensures donors donate and

contribute effortlessly, regardless of their preferred method, thus fostering a broader reach to support needs of the student.

1.2.2 Data Validation

This criterion referred to the procedures the systems used to ensure the validity and legitimacy of the data provided throughout the donation process. Effective data validation helps to ward off fraud and ensure compliance with legal standards. In Give Lively, the application uses Employer Identification Numbers (EINs) to identify nonprofit organizations and verify their status, allowing it to confirm an organization tax-exempt status. To ensure compliance and transparency, EIN provides the application as a tool to verify that an organization or nonprofit meets the legal standards for accountability and tax-exempt status. However, the Donorbox approach offers a more sophisticated set of validation tools than Give Lively. Donorbox uses automated receipts to ensure donors receive proof of contribution immediately, which helps the system verify the legitimacy of campaigns and donations. This focus on validation is crucial, given the open nature of GoFundMe, where anyone creates campaigns for various purposes.

As for EduCash, the application implements a more targeted set of validation measures. This measure includes Donor, student grades, and document verification. This comprehensive validation process is essential to EduCash mission. These measures aimed to ensure that the donations reach genuine college students studying in Bacolod City who meet specific academic performance and financial criteria. These validation measures ensure donor trust and that financial aid reaches only qualified beneficiaries.

1.2.3 Security Measures

This criterion referred to the security metrics of each application employed to protect sensitive data, user information, and financial transactions. Given the nature of online donations, strong security protocols are necessary to protect against data breaches, fraud, and other cyber threats. These metrics help maintain the integrity of the application. Give Lively security measures to create a safe space where users feel confident that their user data is protected. First, it uses end-to-end encryption and Secure Sockets Layer (SSL)-protected pages to ensure that information remains secure and private as it travels between users and the application no prying eyes allowed. Second, data storage is handled thoughtfully. Only essential data is stored, and it is encrypted within the database to keep it safe even if the system is breached. The system does not retain data longer than necessary, which minimizes risk.

Give Lively also partners with top industry players to help ensure everything runs smoothly and securely, so users do not have to worry about outages or vulnerabilities. Finally, through multiple partners, maintain Payment Card Industry (PCI) Level 1 Compliance, the gold standard in payment security, and protect payment data from potential fraud. Donorbox, on the other hand, integrates a large-scale array of security features to protect financial and user data. Just like Give Lively, Donorbox also provides two-factor authentication (2FA) and Fraud detection as security measures. In addition, Donorbox uses tokenization to enhance transaction security. Donorbox also uses Secure Sockets Layer/Transport Layer Security (SSL/TLS) encryption to protect data transmitted between the

Donor and the application, preventing intrusions or interception by malicious actors. Donorbox embedded a fraud-detection system into the application, scanning for unusual patterns and blocking suspicious activity.

Additionally, Donorbox added ReCAPTCHA [RE2007] to distinguish real users from automated systems. ReCAPTCHA helps reduce unauthorized card testing, which in turn helps limit chargeback fees. GoFundMe, on the other hand, integrates fraud detection, data encryption, and PCI compliance to protect user data and ensure safe transactions. Moreover, GoFundMe also focuses on security, but with measures specifically adjusted to ensure remittance security, user authentication, SSL encryption, and PCI compliance. The application puts an emphasis on secure remittance as well as data protection that shields sensitive information, particularly in a student-centered environment where the privacy of the user matters the most.

In contrast to EduCash, the application focuses on security measures to ensure remittance security through a payment gateway. User authentication to ensure that only users have access to the application. SSL encryption protects the data sent to the application. EduCash also implements PCI compliance to prevent misuse of credit cards, debit cards, and cash transactions.

1.2.4 Donor Portal

This criterion refers to the functionalities that enable donors to manage user contributions and track them effectively. This feature also allows donors to review and manage personal information of users and gain visibility into how the contribution of the user is utilized by the system. Lively gives donors a donor

portal as a management tool. It is a feature that allows donors and fundraisers on Give Lively to navigate to user donation history and account details, and to make edits to accounts of users, including updating usernames, email addresses, and passwords. Additionally, the donor portal from Give Lively provides donors and fundraisers with lists of ongoing donations from users. Donors also download donor data in CSV format. As for Donorbox, the feature allows donors to access donation receipts, manage recurring donations, and manage user profiles. GoFundMe, on the other hand, provides a donor portal where users create profiles, track donations, and receive campaign updates, helping donors stay informed about the impact of their contributions and enhancing transparency and engagement on the platform.

In contrast, EduCash implements a donor portal as a donor profile feature, allowing users to donate to scholarship agencies. Then the agencies disbursed funds to eligible students under the application. Donors also access donation history of user, which includes generated receipts showing the username, the amount donated, the scholarship agencies to which the donation of user was sent, and the date and time the donation was made. Additionally, they download the receipt generated by the application from the receipts sent based on the payment gateway used.

1.3 Project Scope

EduCash is a web-based application that aims to financially assist college students who are underprivileged but qualified to benefit from the program, through donations from

NGOs and other individuals. EduCash only serves college students currently academically based in Bacolod City. The following sections provide the discussion that defines the project scope and identifies the project requirements.

1.3.1 Educational Institutions

The application focuses only on institutions that provide undergraduate programs located in Bacolod City. It is home to several universities and colleges. Many students face financial problems that hinder their ability to complete their education. The application primarily focuses on directing financial aid to students from educational institutions in Bacolod City who are in need, helping bridge the gap between available resources and financial constraints.

1.3.2 Target Users

Although the application primarily focuses on Bacolod City, it is not limited to students residing there. It also supports underprivileged yet academically qualified students from other areas, as long as students are academically based in Bacolod City. The main target users include NGOs, private/government agencies, and individual donors who provide financial assistance to qualified recipients. Other users, such as banks and scholarship agencies, are discussed in the subsections that follow.

1.3.2.1 Students

The primary users of the application are the students, or in the terminology adopted for this paper, Underprivileged and qualified college students academically based in Bacolod City, regardless of user residency. The application targets students who

often face financial challenges, such as allowances, school supplies, and even tuition fees. The application prioritizes only those students who illustrate academic excellence and financial need. The application monitors the student academic performance to ensure that only those who deserve it continue to receive financial aid and motivates students to participate and continue to excel academically.

1.3.2.2 Scholarship Agencies

Through the application, scholarship agencies provide students with application forms and efficiently manage the application process. The application enables these agencies to review student profiles and academic performance of the user, and to efficiently select students for further processing or to officially consider them as applicants once matched. In addition, scholarship agencies received funds to be disbursed to students, and the application provides the calculation for distributing those funds those funds based on predefined criteria.

1.3.2.3 Donor

Private/Government agencies, NGO and other specific individuals eager to support the cause are the foundation of the application. Donors provide the monetary resources that are necessary to support user recipients. The application allows them to track user donation history, understand the impact of user

unselfishness. The system also enables donors to view relevant information related to their contributions.

1.3.3 Donations

The application only accepts donations in a monetary form to ensure efficient support for the recipients. EduCash focuses only on financial contributions that enable donors to provide targeted assistance that directly alleviates student educational expenses. The focus of monetary donations is to strengthen the application impact by offering a tangible resource for the recipients or students in need.

1.3.4 Student Requirements

The application aims only to support students who genuinely excel academically. To ensure this, the application provides a set of eligibility criteria for the applicants in the system. These criteria aim to verify that students are part of the cause and need financial assistance. The criteria for qualification focus on the performance of the students in school and require them to meet a certain financial condition to ensure that the donations are distributed to support the students who are serious about user education and create a motivation for the students to maintain their academic progress.

EduCash is a mobile application designed to address the financial gap faced by poor but qualified college students in Bacolod City. By facilitating technology-enabled matching among donors, NGOs, scholarship agencies, and students, EduCash fosters a

culture of philanthropy and social solidarity, in harmony with the vision of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) for inclusive and equitable quality education. Unlike other generic donation applications, EduCash offers an accessible, transparent application that guarantees endowments to qualified individuals and is therefore accountable and honest. With cash disbursements undergoing verifications, data validation, and security measures, it ensures the smoothest, safest way to transact, thereby safeguarding the confidence of every stakeholder. Besides this, immediate matching of scholarships enables optimal resource allocation, thereby ensuring that cash constraints do not hold back successful educational achievers. EduCash not only closes the educational gap but also gives students a chance to realize their dreams, with greater emphasis on social growth and development. An integrated, user-friendly website, EduCash is determined to set standards in educational philanthropy it ensures that a better future is not constrained by financial restrictions on academic ambitions. EduCash strengthens collaboration among donors, NGOs, scholarship agencies, and students through a secure and transparent digital environment. The platform upholds accountability by ensuring that every financial transaction undergoes strict verification and validation processes. By prioritizing qualified beneficiaries, EduCash supports fair and efficient distribution of educational assistance. This project highlights the role of technology in reducing financial barriers and promoting inclusive access to quality education. This capstone project is a testament to the possibility of technology as a catalyst for system-level solutions to dilemmas, ensuring that it paves the way for long-term social change.

CHAPTER II

SYSTEM SPECIFICATIONS

This chapter discusses the general features of the project outlined in the previous chapter. The application provides donors, such as NGOs and other specific individuals, and recipients, who are underprivileged and qualified college students, with an easy way to connect with each other and submit inquiries and receive an initial scholarship screening. The project team aims to support college students by providing financial aid through donations, using the application. The sections that follow introduce the features that enabled the application to achieve its goals and objectives.

2.1 System Perspective and General Perspective

The five general features of the system are illustrated in Figure 1, namely Allowance Distribution, Donor Portal, Scholarship Match, Data Analytics, and Document Verification. By the components presented, components that work together to form the performance process of the application, the project team planned and reviewed the specification to make sure that the development and initiation of the application are successful. Each feature is designed to focus on ensuring a smooth transaction in the application. The project team aims to seamlessly integrate these features to provide a user-friendly, efficient application for donors and recipients. The development process involves a detailed plan and repeated tests to ensure that each feature effectively meets user needs. As presented in the succeeding sections of this chapter, the assumptions and dependencies

are discussed to provide a comprehensive understanding and in-depth analysis of the project that supported and guided its development.

Figure 1. EduCash General Features.

2.1.1 Donor Portal

This feature provided donors with a way to contribute monetarily to support the goal of the project through bank payment integrations, as one-time or recurring donors to the scholarship agencies. Donors also donate through payment gateways integrated into the application, such as PayPal, GCash, and Maya. Individual donors

have the decision to keep themselves as anonymous donors for those who value privacy and do not want to be acknowledged. This feature also provides donors with proof of their donation through an acknowledgement receipt generated by the application. The acknowledgement receipt includes the purpose of the user transaction, which is to donate. The receipt provides the Donor with a view of user transactions, including the amount of the user donation, the agency to which the Donor donated, and the time and date of the transaction.

2.1.2 Scholarship Match

This feature provided students with faster, smoother access to scholarships tailored to students academically based in Bacolod City. Users are able to provide information necessary to apply for a scholarship, including their credentials and performance at school. After which, the system is able to provide them with the scholarship agency to which users credentials are matched. This feature also helps scholarship agencies find qualified students who meet user criteria and user-specific requirements. The requirements set by the scholarship agencies in the applications students fill out serve only as a screening process, not as a direct path to becoming an official applicant for the user program. Only the approval for further transactions is sent to students as a notification.

2.1.2.1 Postings

When used by a scholarship agency, this feature allows that agency to post announcements in the application that are viewable in the interface of the students. Among other matters, this means the agency informs the student of procedures or applications required for the scholarship

application. The application period is also stated, along with contact information and frequently asked questions, all intended to provide a better understanding of the student. When the scholarship agency determines that an announcement is complete and no longer necessary, it is archived. The ability to archive also allows the interface to be managed so that no superfluous announcements are shown to the student. An archive feature enables the agency to revisit any announcement when they need information, as republished announcements are fastened and scholarship-related information is easily tracked.

2.1.3 Data Analytics

The feature displayed on a dashboard includes the total amount of donations collected, the total number of applicants, and the total number of NGO donors, represented in a bar graph, along with a pie chart showing the percentage of individual and anonymous donors. This feature serves as a significant element for the evaluation of the performance of the application. Generation of comprehensive reports to provide users with a valuable awareness of the operation and impact of the application. Specifically, the application provides an analysis and displays key metrics that are discussed further in this section of the paper.

2.1.3.1 Total Amount of Donations Report

The application collects and displays the total amount collected from donors. These data are able to provide a point of reference for the measurement of the fundraising efficiency of the application and to identify the patterns that operate donor contributions. As amounts are monitored,

these serve as substantial indicators of the impact of encouragement on the educational support of the application.

2.1.3.2 Donors Pie Chart

The distinction between the specific NGOs, private/government agencies, individuals, and anonymous donors enabled the application to efficiently accommodate the diverse preferences and motives of donors. Anonymous donors, by contrast, highlighted the importance of privacy and discretion in donating. As for the specific individuals who want to seek acknowledgement for their contributions to users. The application only shows the percentages for individuals, NGOs, private/government agencies, and anonymous donors in a pie chart.

2.1.4 Allowance Distribution

In this feature, students claim financial aid calculated in the application through payment gateways integrated into it. The distribution is scheduled on a specific month each semester, and each time before the distribution, students must submit their academic performance reports. Students must maintain their academic performance as required by the eligibility criteria to avoid being classified as having dropped out as an applicant for the scholarship agency. When the general average falls below the criteria set by the scholarship agency, this allows them to disqualify the applicant from availing the provisions from the scholarship agencies, and the student is not able to match with the scholarship agency for the next period of disbursement until the criteria are met again.

2.1.5 Document Verification

This arguably becomes one of the great features incorporated into the application to sustain the originality and authenticity of the submission of the users. It is the defense that protects the integrity of the application against schemes such as fraudulent submissions and misrepresentation. This set of operations protects the integrity of the identity of the applicants and other assertions in more thorough verification to prove that they are an ethically and legitimately acceptable candidate for the benefited service. It validates uploads from supported documents, academic records, financial statements, and identity proofs through stringent loopholes verification. The system further minimizes errors by checking every document against a reliable database while providing robust security services to detect attempts at crashes and forgeries. With this feature, the application builds confidence among scholarship agencies, helping them earn user trust and aid qualified and well-qualified students.

2.2 Operating Environment

This web-based application supplicates funds from donors, specifically the NGO and other specific individuals who are eager to help in such a cause, enabled students to earn financial support that accords to user academic performance, to ensure increased motivation and engagement in user studies. To ensure a successful development phase, it is essential to identify the hardware and software specifications that supports these tools.

This section outlines the requirements for the development and implementation of this project.

2.2.1 Hardware Requirements

As shown in Table 2, The hardware requirements for development have been carefully selected to ensure optimal performance throughout the project with minimal wasted time. Perhaps the most distinguished member of this list is the AMD Ryzen 5 [AR2007], one of the fastest processors available today, known for its speed and multitasking potential. Such a CPU possesses immense power and efficiency to perform functions such as code compilation, demand management algorithms, and debug tests, all while running the development workstation in the SAF environment. Its multi-core architecture, therefore, provides the much-needed capability to meet performance demands in resource-intensive applications, such as backend processes and online media applications, without consuming additional resources, thus promoting productivity by reducing lag. To complement the process power, 8 GB of DDR4 RAM is included, providing the right amount of reliable memory. This means developers open multiple applications, such as IDEs, version control systems, virtual machines, and browsers for testing, simultaneously with good performance. The project team effortlessly drifts into the code to be debugged and continues testing. Secondary storage ranging from 256 GB to 512 GB SSD, providing a broader range of responsiveness. An SSD reduces the time it takes to start up files and applications, thus booting faster, reading and writing faster, and ultimately maximizing the user experience. More useful in the phase of compilation

and deployment since data and resource access are needed with extraordinary rapidity there.

Component	Development
Processor	AMD Ryzen 5
RAM	8 GB DDR4
Secondary Storage	256GB to 512GB SSD

Table 2. Hardware Recommendations.

2.2.2 Software Requirements

As shown in Table 3, the key software tools used to build the application and the collaboration processes involved. Integrated Environment: Visual Studio Code [VS2021] provides an Integrated IDE with highly flexible, lightweight development and bug-fixing functionality. Git/GitHub [GIT2005] is used for version control to keep project files secure and enable team collaboration. PowerShell acts as an automation and system maintenance scripting terminal for the project team. For front-end development, the project team intends to use Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML), Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), and Bootstrap 5 alongside JavaScript for an interactive user interface. PHP is used for backend development. MySQL is used for database management in the backend. The application is deployed on a Windows 10 or higher workstation. Three communication platforms are used within the project team: Microsoft Teams, Discord, and Google. These modes enable complete interaction among project team members, sensitive planning, real-time coordination, and documentation. All these

software requirements create a complete and well-structured development environment to ensure a successful implementation. The project team developed the prototype using Figma. Such a strategic approach ensures that the application is flexible enough for broad scope and scalable for the future. PHP Mailer is used to send emails for the account creation and management module, and Tesseract OCR for document reading and validation for the document verification module. By integrating these specialized libraries with the core stack, the system achieves a high level of functional automation while maintaining rigorous data integrity.

Component	Software Tool
Integrated Development Environment (IDE)	Visual Code Studio
Version Control	Git/GitHub
Terminals	Power shell
Frontend Development	Hypertext Markup Language (HTML)/ Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)/ JavaScript
Backend Development	PHP, MySQL
Operating System	Windows 10/11
Communication Applications	Microsoft Teams/ Discord
Collaboration Applications	Google Docs
Search Engine	Google Chrome
Prototyping	Figma
Frameworks and Libraries	BOOTSTRAP 5, jQuery
Engines	Tesseract OCR, PHP Mailer

Table 3. Software Recommendations.

2.2.3 Connectivity Requirements

The project requires a stable internet connection and a web browser. An internet connection is essential to ensure smooth integration and uninterrupted operation, allowing online services such as web hosting to be accessed and used with the system. An average speed of 25 Mbps helps ensure the web application operates efficiently, with faster data transfer contributing to a better user experience and greater accessibility. However, if internet speed drops below the specified threshold, problems such as slow downloads and increased latency occurs, negatively impacting the overall user experience.

2.3 Design and Implementation Constraints

In the implementation of this web-based application, there are no systems capable of performing any act without boundaries. In systems development, constraints and difficulties are commonly encountered, such as in user interface design. This section discusses the areas of concern in the development of the application.

2.3.1 Account Creation and Management

The process starts when users try to log in. If users do not have a registered account yet, they must register one. Upon signing up for an account, users are able to choose from the existing roles in the application. For students, the option to be a recipient or a donor is available. As for donors, these user types are categorized as individuals, private or government agencies, or NGOs. As for donor types, one

option is for individual donors to hide their personal identity by remaining anonymous.

2.3.2 Calculation for Distribution

As shown in Table 4, this feature for calculating the distribution of funds to students is one of the fundamental functions of the application. The application provides scholarship agencies with a calculation for distributing funds to students. It starts with calculating the top 20% of scholars for each scholarship agency. This group receives 60% of the total donation amount, divided accordingly. The remaining 80% of the scholars receive 40% of the total amount collected. It is then followed by the same calculations, but for the top 30% of the total number of students in the agency. Another method is to divide it into the top 10 students or the top 20 students and disregard the others. Alternatively, the agencies divide the amount equally among all students.

Calculation	Number of Students	Formula of Distribution
Method 1	Top 20% Priority	60/40 Percent
Method 2	Top 30% Priority	60/40 Percent
Method 3	Top 10 only	Divided Equally
Method 4	Top 20 only	Divided Equally
Method 5	All scholars	Divided Equally

Table 4. Calculation Methods.

2.3.3 Matching Algorithm

The purpose is to develop a well-organized and reliable mechanism for matching student credentials to available scholarships and user qualifications and

needs. In this way, the scholarship application process is seamless, and it ensures that qualified student profiles are matched with relevant funding sources. Scholarship agencies define eligibility criteria, and the system uses them to accurately match students. The matching of criteria is defined by student academic requirements, such as the general weighted average of the student. Another requirement is the financial situation of user, demographics, and special qualifications. Scholarship agencies also set the deadline for the matching phase; once the current date passes the deadline, they are no longer visible to students.

2.3.4 Color-coded Interface

As shown in Table 5, to consolidate some portions of the user interface, the project team decided to implement a color-coded scheme for each account type, ensuring consistency and minimizing potential confusion in navigating the system. The use of distinct background colors allows users to quickly identify their account type and enhances the overall usability of the application. For the student account, the background color is set to white, symbolizing simplicity and clarity. At the same time, for donors, the interface adopts a subtle shade of blue that represents trust and reliability. In contrast, the scholarship agency accounts are assigned a subtle green background, signifying growth and opportunity. Despite these differences, there is a shared section of the UI accessible to all account types: the dashboard within the reports interface. To maintain uniformity, the background color in this section is a subtle red, chosen to emphasize the data presented. Meanwhile, the admin interface features a black background, providing a strong, authoritative design that distinguishes it from the other account types.

Interface/Account Type	Background Color
Admin Account	Black
Student Account	White
Donor Account	Light Blue
Scholarship Agency Account	Light Green
Reports Interface	Light Yellow

Table 5. Color-coded Interface.

2.4 Ethical Considerations

This section discusses the ethical considerations observed in the development of EduCash, particularly in relation to the use of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, with further details provided in Appendix J. Given that the application processes sensitive student records, financial transactions, and user submitted documents, ethical responsibility is essential to ensure data accuracy, transparency, privacy, and responsible technology use. The development team adhered to ethical guidelines that promote accountability, user trust, and compliance with acceptable use policies of third-party services.

2.4.1 Ethical Use of Application Programming Interface (API)

EduCash integrates several third-party APIs, including payment gateway services such as PayPal API, GCash API, and Maya API, as well as SMTP email services through PHPMailer to send system-generated notifications and receipts. These APIs were used strictly in accordance with their respective terms of service and licensing agreements. EduCash accesses user financial and account-related data only with explicit user action and consent, and solely for application functions such

as donation processing, receipt generation, and transaction confirmation. No sensitive financial credentials such as full card numbers, PINs, or password are stored within the EduCash database, as all transactions are securely handled through the official payment providers. Personally identifiable information is not shared beyond what is necessary for system operation and verification.

2.4.2 Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools

Artificial Intelligence tools were utilized to support both application development and document processing. Tesseract OCR was used to assist in extracting text from uploaded student documents such as grades, certificates, and identification files to support the document verification feature. In addition, ChatGPT was used as a supporting tool for drafting portions of documentation, refining technical descriptions, and assisting during system development. These tools did not replace human judgment or academic authorship but served only as productivity aids under developer supervision. All outputs generated with AI assistance were carefully reviewed, edited, and validated by the project team to maintain academic integrity, originality, and accuracy. EduCash prioritizes responsible data handling, user consent, and oversight in all AI-assisted processes.

2.5 Assumptions and Dependencies

This section of the paper covers conditions and factors required for the successful development, deployment, and operation of the application. It identifies key expectations and external influences that possibly affects project implementation and maintenance. Such

factors are very important to identify for risk management purposes and ensure alignment with the goals of the project.

2.5.1 Assumptions

These are beliefs and forecast variables that direct project development and implementation. Assumptions provide a framework for understanding the intended future position of systems under defined criteria and for explaining resources. Explicitly stated are the assumptions identified for user importance and implications for the application. These are important for setting the project scope and limits, thereby facilitating all stakeholders in developing a standard unit of expectation. These assumptions provide the basis for planning for all possible risks and challenges. In addition, these provide a good basis for making decisions throughout development regarding design choices and resource allocation. User identification and validation play a key role in the sustainability of the application. These standardize the process and improve project success.

2.5.1.1 Financially Assist the Recipients

One of the major assumptions of the application ensures that it targets a group of students in serious financial need while maintaining excellent academic standards. The focus of the application to aid qualified college students fosters accountability and transparency since it only targets students who are qualified to receive financial support. The application provides a concentrated impact and efficient evaluation by focusing only on students academically based in Bacolod City. This allows the system to

better monitor eligibility, academic performance, and proper distribution of financial assistance within its intended scope.

2.5.1.2 Eager Donors to use Payment Gateways

This assumption is grounded in the growth trend of digital payment adoption. The application offers a range of payment options, including PayPal, GCash, and Maya, improving its accessibility and donor experience. This assumption supports the general adoption of digital wallets and traditional bank services, as well as increased donation opportunities. It mitigates barriers for donors who prefer specific payment gateways. By maintaining the security of financial transactions across multiple payment gateways requires technical safeguards.

2.5.1.3 Retention Policy for Student Academic Standard

This assumption incentivizes academic performance and aligns the distribution of financial support with the principles of excellence. The application monitors students who are consistent with academic performance of users to avoid being classified as dropped in the application and to continue receiving the support the students deserve. This is to ensure that monetary donations are received by students who are genuinely committed to user education. This motivates the student applicants or scholars to actively engage with the application and user academics. A termination note is issued to the student because their credentials did not meet the eligibility criteria for continued financial support. However,

students are still able to look for a scholarship agency that best matches their academic eligibility and financial status.

2.5.2 Dependencies

These refer to criteria, systems, or elements that are required externally for the success of the development, implementation, and operation of the project. These influence the functionality of the application and ensure that the objectives are met productively. EduCash depends on partnerships, technological assets that are essential for absolute transparency between donors and recipients. The following discusses the dependencies that are critical for the reduction and mitigation of risks, and to ensure that the alignment of the project with the needs of the user and expectations.

2.5.2.1 Security Measures

The application heavily relies on robust security measures to protect sensitive data as it is transmitted between servers, ensured the integrity and privacy of financial transactions and user information. To safeguard student accounts, the application implements Two-Factor Authentication (2FA), added an extra layer of security that required users to verify user identity through a secondary method. The use of SSL encryption ensures that all data transmitted is securely encrypted, prevented unauthorized access in the time of transfer. By to adhere to PCI Compliance standards, the application ensures that payment and credit card information is handled with the highest level of security, reduced risks associated with financial fraud.

The chapter outlines the guidelines for the system specification process for EduCash, a web-based application designed to provide grants by selecting scholarships based on assessments of needy students. It presents a balance of financial needs and education availability through the donor portal, scholarship matching, data analytics, allowance distribution, and document verification, which together form the core components of the system and operate in an integrated manner to ensure a transparent, efficient, and reliable platform for all users. The donor portal enables users to create accounts, browse student profiles, and contribute anonymously or publicly, while tracking transaction history and issuing receipts to maintain transparency and accountability, allowing donors to monitor contributions and verify fund allocation. Scholarship matching uses algorithms to connect qualified students with appropriate grants based on academic performance and financial assessments, ensuring fair and equitable distribution of financial assistance according to defined eligibility criteria. Data analytics provide detailed insights into donor preferences, scholarship distributions, and student performance, allowing administrators to optimize policies, monitor trends, and support informed for continuous system improvement. Document verification validates academic credentials, financial records, and identity submissions to preserve system credibility, strengthen trust among all stakeholders, and reduce the risk of inaccurate or fraudulent information. Allowance distribution follows predefined rules to ensure fair and timely release of financial assistance based on eligibility status and approved calculations, contributing to a consistent, regulated, and transparent process, and collectively supporting the goal of effective, sustainable, and trustworthy scholarship management.

CHAPTER III

SYSTEM FEATURES

This chapter outlines the features of the application, which are intended to foster smooth interaction among scholarship agencies, donors, and students. It describes the system goals as improved efficiency and teamwork. Students in need apply for scholarships with greater ease thanks to a system that streamlines the application and financing processes. Activity diagrams and functional requirements illustrate the methods, highlight key user actions, and discuss the system responses in the following sections.

3.1 System Decomposition

As shown in Figure 2, each module is designed to streamline specific application functions and create a unified application that bridges the gap between qualified students and compassionate donors. Together, these modules ensure that the application is user-friendly, transparent, and impactful. The decomposition chart of the application highlights four essential modules that ensure its functionality and user-friendly design. First, the account creation and management module provides users with a centralized, personalized space within the application. This module enables users to sign in, sign up, or edit their user information regardless of their role. Second is the scholarship matching module, which matches students with suitable scholarship agencies based on their academic credentials. Third is the financial transactions module, which handles all user transactions, including financial transactions, and provides a method for calculating disbursements. For instance,

this module allows donors to make donations via payment gateways. Lastly, the dashboard module provides all users with a data analytics report in the application. This module also includes the admin dashboard, where the admin is able to monitor scholarship agencies to verify the account registration and handling documents.

Figure 2. EduCash Decomposition Chart.

3.2 System Functionalities

In this section of the chapter, the project team provided details about the information of each module within the application. The subsequent sections presented an outline of how these functionalities are used during user interactions, the corresponding system responses, and the underlying backend integration. The project team employed activity diagrams to illustrate the workflow of each module. These diagrams served as a

visual representation of the behavior of the system, enhancing the understanding of the logical sequence of actions and improving the overall quality of the design of the application

3.2.1 Account Creation and Management

The module for creating and managing of account is the most important feature in the application. This application function provides all users with a secure, personalized space for a better user experience. This module allowed users to sign up for a new account and log in to their registered accounts. This functionality also allowed users to edit some personal information, such as email addresses, contact numbers, and passwords. This also comes with an email verification for more security and integrity in the application.

3.2.1.1 Description and Priority

The account creation and management module handles all account registration, login, and modification, which is the first step all users must take. Regardless of the role of the user, all users follow the same functionality with different forms to fill out personal information and necessary documents that are required for validation and verification. Users choose from three account types: student, donor, and scholarship agency. The application recognizes the account type and saves the data to the database. The application retrieves the credentials when the user logs in to their account and directs them to a specific user interface based on their account type. Proper account management ensures that each user interacts

only with features relevant to their assigned role, maintaining appropriate access and system security.

3.2.1.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

As mentioned in the previous main section, the account creation and management module provided the users with a centralized space for all account types. And users have the option to choose from different roles, such as student, donor, and scholarship agency. As for the scholarship agency, before having access to the features of the application, the admin monitors the scholarship agency accounts and provides a message for further verification of the account. This functionality is further discussed in the following sections of this chapter. And once logged in, the application checks the account type of the user so that the users are headed to their respective user interface. As shown in Table 6, the activity diagram provides a visual representation of the flow for sign-up, log-in, and user data modification. The flow starts when the user chooses to register or log in to an existing account. Upon registration, the user must provide necessary information, such as an email address, name, contact information, and password. The application then sends a verification token to the email address provided by the user. Once the email has been verified, the user is now able to log in and have access to the application features. The user is also able to edit user data once logged in. However, logging in to an account that is not verified via email results in a jQuery error message prompting that the email is not yet verified.

Function Name	Account Creation and Management
Function Description	This function allowed the users to create, log in, and edit other personal information.
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Upon registration, users are requested to choose an account type ○ Upon log in, users must have a verified account. ○ Upon modifying personal data, users must log in to an account.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The user is now able to access the features of the application.
Activity Flow	
User	EduCash
<pre> graph TD subgraph User Start(()) --> Register{Register an account?} Register -- yes --> SignUp[Sign up] SignUp --> InputInfo[Input personal Information] InputInfo --> LogIn[Log in] LogIn --> InputCred[Input Credentials] end subgraph EduCash InputCred --> CredValid{Credentials valid?} CredValid -- yes --> UserLoggedIn[user logged in] CredValid -- No --> PromptError1[prompt error message] SignUp --> InputVer[Input Verification Code] InputVer --> SendEmail[Send email verification] SendEmail --> Valid{Valid?} Valid -- yes --> SaveData[Save user data] SaveData --> End(()) Valid -- No --> PromptError2[prompt error message] end LogIn --> PromptError1 UserLoggedIn --> Register </pre>	
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ On the registration interface, a button is visible that allows the user to head back to the log in interface.
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ User inputs invalid credentials or a non-verified account results to a prompted error message.

Table 6. Account Creation and Management Activity Diagram.

3.2.1.3 Functional Requirements

The project team outlined the task needed to utilize the functionality of the account creation and management feature. Given two options, if the user does not have an existing account, three buttons are available to click based on the desired account type. If the user already has an account, a log in form is directly displayed after the splash page of the application, where students are able to input the credentials that match against the database for verification and secure access to the system.

- a. The log in form is displayed in the right-hand side and is beside the logo of the application.
- b. By inputting the credentials in the log in form heads the user to the profile page if credentials are matched and valid.
- c. If the user is not verified through email, an error message is prompted.
- d. Three buttons are displayed under the log in form for account registration.
- e. By clicking the button results to different registration forms.
- f. After a successful registration a token for verification is sent to the given email address.
- g. The email provides a link to the application.
- h. Invalid tokens result to a prompted error message.
- i. If the account is a scholarship agency, the admin is notified.

3.2.2 Scholarship Matching

The module for the matching feature is an essential feature of the application, followed by the account creation and management module. This functionality benefits the two users of the application: students and scholarship agencies. This feature allows the scholarship agencies to post information and procedures for scholarship applications and set criteria for students to match.

3.2.2.1 Description and Priority

This scholarship-matching feature requires scholarship agencies to set criteria and for students to upload documents. This feature also includes postings that allow the agencies to provide students with information about their programs. The students scroll through their feed, which provides scholarship information.

3.2.2.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

As mentioned in the main section, this feature allows the students to match with a scholarship agency based on their qualifications and the set eligibility criteria or scroll through postings of the scholarship agency. Table 7 illustrates the flow of the feature. For students, it starts with checking whether the documents are up to date or valid. As for the scholarship agency, criteria must be set so they are visible when students are looking for a match. When a match is found, students click the apply button and be redirected to an application form. The scholarship agencies are then notified when a student applies.

3.2.2.3 Functional Requirements

The project team outlined the tasks needed to use the scholarship matching and postings feature. The scholarship agencies set the criteria for matching, and the students are matched based on their eligibility and academic performance. The scholarship matching feature is accessible through the navbar menu: "criteria" for scholarship agencies and "scholarship" for students. However, the postings feature is accessible in the "feed" navbar menu for students and in the "post" navbar menu for scholarship agencies.

- a. The students click on “Feed” on the navbar.
- b. The posts from scholarship agencies are displayed.
- c. Students are provided with the information and procedures for application.
- d. The scholarship agencies click on “Post”, and the form are displayed.
- e. Scholarship agencies are able to provide the information and procedures for application.
- f. For matching, the scholarship agencies click on “criteria”, and a form are displayed.
- g. Students click on “Scholarships”, and a match appears.
- h. If the student has invalid or missing documents, an error message appears.
- i. Scholarship agencies are required to set criteria for matching.

3.2.3 Financial Transactions

This module comprises two major functionalities: donation and allowance distribution. Allowance distribution also includes one functionality of this module: the calculation methods which is discussed further in the previous chapter. The donate feature is accessible to users with donor accounts. At the same time, the allowance distribution feature is accessible to users with a scholarship agency account.

3.2.3.1 Description and Priority

The financial transaction feature is the core functionality and primary purpose of the implementation of this application. This feature allows donors to contribute funds directly to a scholarship agency based on specific criteria, such as the location of the student or the minimum academic average required for eligibility. Donors select their preferred payment method, ensuring that the donation process is secure, convenient, and transparent. Once the donation is received, scholarship agencies use the funds to disburse financial support to scholars according to the calculation method defined for each program. The disbursement process is facilitated through integrated payment gateways, enabling timely and accurate transfers while maintaining records of all financial transactions in the application.

3.2.3.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

As mentioned in the previous section, this feature handles all financial transactions in the application, including sending donations to

scholarship agencies, distributing allowances to students, and selecting calculation methods. Illustrated in Table 8 is the visualizations of the flow of the process in the financial transactions of the application. The donation process starts when the donor navigates to the donate button in the navbar menu. After clicking the button, a form appears with two dropdown inputs. The donor is then able to input criteria such as the location of the scholarship agency and the minimum average requirement for student eligibility. After the donor submits the form, scholarship agencies that meet the criteria appear in a tabular format. If no scholarship agencies are found, an error message is displayed. Another flow aside from donating is to view the scholars of those scholarship agencies. Upon clicking the donate button, the donor is directed to the interface where payment methods are displayed. After a successful transaction, the donor is requested to upload the donation receipt to inform the scholarship agency that the transaction has occurred. As for the scholarship agency, after receiving the donation, the donors are displayed in the inbox section alongside the payment method, amount, and donation date. Scholarship agencies acknowledge the donation to inform the donor that the transaction went through and that the funds have been received. When the time comes for the scholarship agency to disburse the money, a calculation method is first set, and the disbursement is based on that method. The students also confirm that the allowance distribution has been received via email by clicking the acknowledgement button in the inbox section, where the allowance distribution history is located.

Function Name	Donate	
Function Description	This feature allows the donors to donate to scholarship agencies.	
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The account requires to be a donor account. ○ Scholarship agencies are required to upload QR code. 	
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Donors successfully donated to scholarship agencies. ○ Scholarship Agencies receive a receipt to acknowledge. 	
Activity Flow		
Donor	EduCash	Scholarship Agency
<pre> graph TD subgraph Donor Start(()) --> Click[Click "Donate" Button] Click --> Prompt[prompt message about the payment gateway current state] Prompt --> Filter[filter base on location of the scholarship agency and minimum average required] Filter --> Save[save donation history] Save --> End(()) end subgraph EduCash Filter -- No --> PromptNo[prompt "no scholarship agency found"] Filter -- Yes --> Display[Display Scholarship Agencies] Display --> SelectAgency[Select a scholarship agency] SelectAgency --> SelectGateway[Select from partially integrated payment gateway] SelectGateway --> Upload[upload receipt] Upload --> SaveHistory[save donation history] end subgraph ScholarshipAgency Upload --> Donation[Donation received] Donation --> Acknowledge[acknowledge receipt] end </pre>		
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aside from donating, the donors are able to view the scholars of the scholarship agency. ○ A button is visible on top to go back to the previous page. 	
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ An error prompt appears when there are no agencies found. 	

Table 8. Donate Activity Diagram.

As mentioned in the previous section, this feature focuses on the allowance distribution process of the application, specifically the disbursement of funds from scholarship agencies to qualified students. Presented in Table 9 is the activity flow that illustrates how allowance distribution is carried out within the EduCash system. The process begins when a scholarship agency logs into a verified agency account and selects a preferred calculation method for distributing allowances. After setting the calculation method, the agency provides the list of students together with the computed allowance amounts based on the chosen calculation. Once the details are reviewed and confirmed, the scholarship agency initiates the disbursement by clicking the disburse button and selecting an appropriate payment gateway. Upon successful transfer of funds, the system prompts the agency to upload a receipt, which is automatically stored and reflected in the allowance disbursement history for monitoring and auditing purposes. On the student side, beneficiaries receive their allowances and are required to acknowledge receipt through the system interface. This acknowledgement triggers an automated email notification to the scholarship agency, confirming that the allowance has been successfully received. In cases where no eligible students or agencies are found, the system displays an error prompt to guide the user, while navigation controls are also provided to allow users to return to the previous page. Overall, this feature ensures transparency, accountability, and proper documentation throughout the allowance distribution process.

Function Name	Allowance Distribution	
Function Description	This feature allows the scholarship agencies to disburse money to students.	
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The account requires to be a scholarship agency account. ○ Students are required to upload QR code. ○ Before disbursement, scholarship agencies select a method of calculation. 	
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Scholarship agencies successfully disbursed money to students. ○ Students received the remittance. 	
Activity Flow		
Scholarship Agency	EduCash	Students
<pre> graph TD subgraph SA [Scholarship Agency] Start(()) --> S1[Select a calculation method] S2[Select a payment gateway] --> End1(()) End2[acknowledgement] --> End1 end subgraph EduCash S1 --> S3[provide list of students with the amount to be distributed based on calculation] S3 --> S4[Click the disburse icon] S4 --> S5[Select a payment gateway] S5 --> S6[upload receipt] S6 --> S7[save disbursement history] end subgraph Students S6 --> S8[allowance received] S8 --> S9[acknowledge receipt] end S9 --> End2 </pre>		
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aside from donating, the donors are able to view the scholars of the scholarship agency. ○ A button is visible on top to go back to the previous page. 	
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ An error prompt appears when there are no agencies found. 	

Table 9. Allowance Distribution Activity Diagram.

3.2.3.3 Functional Requirements

The project team outlined the tasks required to use the financial transactions feature. The donation process is accessible to donors via the navbar menu "Donate," and a form appears for donors to enter criteria such as location and the minimum average required by the scholarship agencies. The allowance distribution process is accessible to scholarship agencies through the navbar menu "disbursement".

- a. The donors click “Donate” in the navbar and are headed to input a form.
- b. The donors input the location and minimum average requirement of the scholarship agency.
- c. An error message is prompted when there are no scholarship agencies found.
- d. The donors click the view button on the “actions” column, and a list of scholars are displayed.
- e. Donors click the donate button and select a payment gateway.
- f. Donors upload the receipt as proof of donation.
- g. The scholarship agencies received the donation.
- h. An email is sent to the scholarship agencies after a successful donation from donors.
- i. The scholarship agencies click on the inbox menu in the sidebar.
- j. The list of donors who donated is displayed in a tabular format.

- k. The scholarship agencies click the eye icon in the “Receipt” column to view the receipt.
- l. The scholarship agencies click the thumbs up icon in the “Actions” column to acknowledge the receipt.
- m. An email is sent to the donor to notify that the scholarship agency has received the donation.
- n. After selecting a calculation method, the list of scholars is displayed in a tabular format and a disburse button appears.
- o. The students are sorted according to the average.
- p. The data displayed in the tabular format includes the average of the students, the amount to disbursed and the name of the students.
- q. When the scholarship agency clicks on the bank icon on the “Actions” column, the interface is redirected to where the payment methods appear.
- r. The scholarship agency selects a payment method.
- s. The QR Code of the students appear.
- t. The scholarship agency scans the QR code of the student.
- u. After a successful transaction, the scholarship agency is requested to upload the receipt of the transaction.
- v. The student received the allowance disbursed.
- w. The student clicks on the acknowledgement icon.

3.2.4 Dashboard

The module for data display consists of two features: scholarship monitoring in the admin dashboard and a data analytics report. These data analytics reports are displayed in various representations and are accessible to all users in the application. This feature also allows the admin to monitor non-verified scholarship agencies and communicate through email using the application.

3.2.4.1 Description and Priority

The data analytics report provides users with different data representations of reports in the application. However, this application feature requires user data to track the total donation amount, the number of registered students over time, and comparisons across donor types. Additionally, the scholarship monitoring feature is only used by the admin. This is to ensure the legitimacy of the scholarship agency.

3.2.4.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

As shown in Table 10, the process flow for the Scholarship Monitoring feature of the dashboard module. The process is initiated whenever a scholarship agency registers in the EduCash application. Upon registration, the scholarship agency must submit the required verification documents before gaining access to system functionalities. The administrator then reviews the submitted documents through the admin dashboard to assess the legitimacy of the scholarship agency. If the submitted requirements are complete and valid, the administrator verifies the scholarship agency, allowing it to fully access the platform. When

submitted documents are incomplete or missing, the system displays an error message, preventing verification until all requirements are met.

Function Name	Scholarship Monitoring	
Function Description	This function allows the admin to monitor non-verified scholarship agencies in the application.	
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To monitor scholarship agencies, the account must be an admin account. 	
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The admin has now verified the scholarship agency. 	
Activity Flow		
Admin	EduCash	Scholarship Agency
<pre> graph TD subgraph Admin Start(()) --> ShowList[show list of non-verified scholarship agency] SendEmailAdmin[Send email to scholarship agency] end subgraph EduCash VerifyUser[Verify the user] Decision{Missing/suspicious files?} Verified[Scholarship agency is verified] end subgraph ScholarshipAgency SendEmailAgency[Send email notification] End(()) end ShowList --> VerifyUser VerifyUser --> Decision Decision -- Yes --> SendEmailAdmin Decision -- No --> Verified SendEmailAdmin --> SendEmailAgency Verified --> SendEmailAgency SendEmailAgency --> End </pre>		
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A button is visible for the admin to view the data analytics report. 	
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Admin verifies the scholarship agency while having missing files results to an error message. 	

Table 10. Scholarship Monitoring Activity Diagram.

Table 11, on the other hand, presents the process flow of the Data Analytics Report feature. This process begins when a user clicks the Report button located on the sidebar of the application. Once activated, the system retrieves relevant data and displays it in various graphical and chart-based representations. These reports allow users to monitor donation transactions, user registrations, and other system-related statistics. The feature includes navigation controls that enable users to return to the previous page.

Function Name	Data Analytics Report
Function Description	This function allows the users to keep track of the transactions through different data representations.
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any user types or account types are able to access the feature.
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The application provides the users graphs and charts of the data analytics reports.
Activity Flow	
User	EduCash
<pre> graph TD Start(()) --> Click[Click "Reports" Button] Click --> Pie[Display donor pie chart] Click --> Students[Display chart for number of students in monthly interval] Click --> Donations[Display line chart for total donations in monthly interval] Pie --> End((())) Students --> End Donations --> End </pre>	
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Users are provided with a button that heads back to the previous page.
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow internet connection results to the data not being displayed.

Table 11. Data Analytics Report Activity Diagram.

3.2.4.3 Functional Requirements

The project team outlined the processes required to use the dashboard module functionality. Upon clicking the reports section in the sidebar, users are taken to a page where the data is displayed in different representations, such as graphs and charts. Users track the total amount of donations in the application, the total number of students registered over time, and comparisons across donor types. As for the scholarship agency monitoring feature exclusively for the admin, scholarship agencies are monitored in the admin dashboard. Every time a scholarship agency is registered, it appears in the admin dashboard as a non-verified account. The admin has the power to view the documents submitted by the scholarship agencies. It is also possible for the admin to email the scholarship agency through the application whenever the admin believes the submitted documents are suspicious or require clarification. Once the admin validates the documents, the scholarship agency is now fully verified and has access to the system features.

- a. User clicks on reports button in the sidebar.
- b. Data are displayed in the dashboard through graphs and charts.
- c. Click the button “Go back” to return to the previous page.
- d. Scholarship agency registers an account.
- e. Scholarship agency is now classified as non-verified.
- f. Scholarship agencies are displayed into the admin dashboard.
- g. The admin is able to view the submitted documents.

- h. If the admin tried to verify the agency while having no documents submitted, an error message is prompted.
- i. Admin is able to send email to the scholarship agency through the application.
- j. Admin is notified when a scholarship agency has uploaded new documents.

In conclusion, this chapter has outlined the system features of the application, designed to enhance interaction between different account types such as students, donors, scholarship agencies, and the admin. The chapter introduces four major functionalities that support the implementation and development of the application. The project team provided a decomposition chart and activity diagrams to illustrate the major functions of the system. Flow charts or activity diagrams provided a visual illustration of the process flows of the system features, such as the account creation and management, scholarship matching, financial transactions, and the dashboard module. Together with the flowcharts are the preconditions, postconditions, alternate flows, and exception flows that handle errors and prompt error messages, providing a high-quality, user-friendly interface that improves the user experience.

CHAPTER IV

EXTERNAL INTERFACE REQUIREMENTS

The external interface of the EduCash project encompasses several key components that enhance the user experience and facilitate seamless interactions within the application. This chapter outlines the specifications and various user interfaces, including the login page, reports dashboard, donation interfaces, matching interfaces, user profiles, and many more. Each of these interfaces played a major role in ensuring user satisfaction and the efficient use of the EduCash project. By addressing the specific requirements and characteristics of these user interfaces, EduCash delivered a comprehensive, intuitive application for user access and provided educational and financial assistance to students in Bacolod City.

4.1 User Interfaces

The screen layouts of the EduCash application are the gateway through which donors, students, and scholarship agencies together with the admin interact with one another. The user interfaces encompass the interactive and visual elements that enabled the seamless access to features and navigation. This section of the chapter explores the principles, usability, and the layout that ensures an intuitive and engaging user experience. EduCash provided a color-coded interface depending on the user types to prevent confusion and by consolidating the background color to identify different account types such as donors, scholarship agencies, and students.

4.1.1 Login Page

The page for logging in of the EduCash application, shown in Figure 3, provides a user-friendly interface for secure account access. Besides the logo, two input fields are provided for users to enter their email address and password. A forgot password hyperlink is provided below if the user ever forgets his/her password. By clicking the login button, users are redirected to the user profile page and access system features. However, if the user is not registered yet, the three buttons below serve as user account types, each leading to different input fields.

The screenshot displays the login interface for the EduCash application. On the left side, there is a logo featuring a blue silhouette of a person wearing a graduation cap, set against a green circular background with a dashed line and a green arrow pointing downwards. Below the logo, the text "EduCash" is written in a blue and green font. On the right side, there is a light blue login form. It contains an "Email" input field with the placeholder text "@ e.g example@gmail.com". Below that is a "Password" input field with the placeholder text "Enter your Password" and a toggle icon. Under the password field, there is a checkbox for "Remember me" and a link for "Forgot password?". A black "Sign In" button is positioned below these options. Further down, there is a link for "Don't have an account?" and a "Register as" section with three buttons: "Student", "Donor", and "Agency".

Figure 3. Login Interface.

4.1.2 Forgot Password

As shown in Figure 4, the forgot password form interface of the EduCash application. If the user ever forgets their password, an email input field is provided, and the application sends a six-digit verification code to the email address of user. After the user enters the email address, clicking the button takes them to another page to continue the process. After redirecting, another input field appears where the user enters the six-digit verification code.

The figure displays two sequential steps of the 'Forgot your password?' process. The first step shows an email input field and a 'Send reset code' button. The second step shows a confirmation message and a 6-digit code input field with a 'Verify code' button.

Figure 4. Forgot Password Interface.

4.1.3 Student Registration Page

As shown in Figure 5, when the user decides to register as a student, the student button is accessible at the bottom left of the login form. When clicked, the user is redirected to the form where they register a student account. The form includes the full name of the student, the school where the student is currently enrolled, the contact number of the student, the program of study, the email address, the date of birth, and the password confirmation. Upon clicking the continue button, the account is now processed for verification. A button is also available if the user already has an account and wants to return to the login form.

The screenshot displays a registration form titled "Create a Student Account". The form is organized into two columns of input fields. The left column contains fields for "Full Name", "Contact.", "Email", and "Password". The right column contains fields for "Search School", "Search Program", a date field with the placeholder "mm/dd/yyyy" and a calendar icon, and "Confirm Password". Below the input fields, there is a large "Continue" button and a smaller link that says "Already have an account? Sign in".

Figure 5. Student Registration Interface.

4.1.4 Upload Credentials Form

As shown in Figure 6, once a student is registered and has logged in to an existing student account, the student is then redirected to the form where necessary documents and files are uploaded and validated by the application. The students are required to upload the certificate of enrolment, a validated school ID, and a certified true copy of their grades for the application to verify that the user is currently enrolled. To verify that the student is in need or underprivileged when it comes to the financial aspect, some documents are required to be submitted, which include the certificate of indigency and the proof of income of the parents of the student. The application aims only to support students who are underprivileged but deserving and have commendable academic performance.

Upload Credentials

Upload certified true copy of grades

Upload certificate of enrolment

Upload validated school ID

Upload Certificate of Indigency

Upload Proof of Income

Submit

Figure 6. Upload Credentials Interface.

4.1.5 Duplicate File Error

As shown in Figure 7, upon submission of the documents submitted by the students, the application then validates and verifies the data. In instance where the student has uploaded a duplicate file, the application detects and provide the students a prompt error message. The prompted error message tells the students that the documents submitted has duplicate, and the student must select another file or document to upload. By clicking the OK button head backs the student to the form and the student is now able to continue uploading the files and documents for the application to process and validate.

Figure 7. Duplicate File Error Interface.

4.1.6 Student Profile

After successfully submitting the required files and documents, the application validates and verifies them. The student is now able to access the scholarship-matching feature. In the login interface, it shows the name of the student, the personal information such as contact number, email address, and the monthly income of the parents of the student on the left side of the main content of the screen. On the right side, the academic information of the student is shown, which includes the school where the student is enrolled, the program of study of the student, and the average grade in the previous semester. There are two buttons accessible to the student: the update credentials and edit profile buttons. The update credentials button leads to the form where students upload documents, which is shown in Figure 8.

The screenshot displays a student profile interface. At the top, there is a circular profile picture of a student in a white t-shirt with a red heart and the text 'I ❤️ DATA SCIENCE'. Below the photo are two buttons: 'Update Photo' and 'Submit'. The student's name, 'Kessel John Vingno', is centered below the photo. The profile is divided into two columns: 'Personal Information' and 'Academic Information'. The 'Personal Information' column lists the email 'kessel@gmail.com', contact number '+639652632323', and parent's monthly income '12,000.00'. The 'Academic Information' column lists the school 'University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)', program 'Bachelor of Science in Information Technology', and average grade '94.63 %'. At the bottom of the interface are two buttons: 'Update Credentials' and 'Edit Profile'.

Personal Information	Academic Information
Email kessel@gmail.com	School University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)
Contact +639652632323	Program Bachelor of Science in Information Technology
Parent's Monthly Income 12,000.00	Average 94.63 %

Figure 8. Student Profile Interface.

4.1.7 Scholarship Feed

When the user clicks the Feed section in the side navigation bar, the student is taken to the feed section, where information about scholarship agencies is posted. The student is able to gather information about specific scholarships, including their requirements and application procedures. As shown in Figure 9 is the interface of the feed of postings from the scholarship agencies. It provides the name of the scholarship agency, the scholarship benefits, eligibility and application requirements, the submission deadline, the announcement date for results, and contact information.

Mcdo Agency

<h3 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Scholarship Benefits</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Monthly Living Allowance ✓ Health and Wellness Support ✓ Employment Assistance After Graduation 	<h3 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Eligibility Requirements</h3> <p>With Degree programs related to:</p> <p>✗ With minimum grade requirement of [90% - 95%]</p>
<h3 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Application Requirements</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📄 Certified True Copy of Grades or Transcript of Records 📄 Certificate of Enrollment or Admission 📄 Copy of Valid School ID 📄 Income Tax Return (ITR) of parents/guardian 📄 Certificate of Indigency from Barangay/Municipality 	<h3 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Application Process</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔗 register 🔗 apply
<p>📅 Deadline of Submission: [2025-05-28]</p> <p>📅 Announcement of Result: [2025-06-07]</p>	
<p>For more inquiries, contact us as 📞 [+2147483647] or ✉ [mcdo@gmail.com]</p>	

Figure 9. Feed Interface.

4.1.8 Matched Scholarships

Upon clicking the scholarship section in the side navigation bar, the student is redirected to a page where scholarships that match their credentials are displayed. As shown in Figure 10, the scholarship agencies matched the qualifications and living conditions of the students. The interface also displays the application deadline and the scholarship agencies profile photo.

Figure 10. Matched Scholarships Interface.

4.1.9 Application Form

After the student clicks the "apply now" button, they are redirected to the application form. As shown in Figure 11, the application form is where students fill it out and submit it to the scholarship agency. The application form asks the student to explain why they deserve the scholarship in at least 200 words. To guide students on the number of words being typed, a word counter is provided at the bottom-right of the text area. After the student reaches a minimum of 200 words, a button at the bottom center is displayed, and upon clicking it, the student application is sent to the scholarship agency.

Why do you deserve this Scholarship? (Please write a minimum of 200 words)

I believe I deserve this scholarship because I am committed to achieving academic excellence while using my education to create meaningful impact in my community. Throughout my academic journey, I have consistently demonstrated dedication, perseverance, and a strong work ethic, even in the face of financial challenges. My passion for learning drives me to continuously improve myself, not only for personal success but also to contribute to the betterment of society.

Receiving this scholarship would greatly ease my financial burden, allowing me to focus more on my studies and participate in academic and community initiatives that foster growth and development. I plan to use my knowledge and skills to help address pressing issues in my community, such as improving access to education and creating opportunities for underprivileged youth.

This scholarship represents more than just financial assistance; it is an opportunity to further develop my potential, enhance my leadership abilities, and give back to those who have supported me along the way. I am determined to maximize this opportunity and uphold the values of hard work, responsibility, and service. With your support, I can continue striving toward my academic goals and become a positive force for change. Thank you and God Bless!

Words: 201

Submit Application

Figure 11. Application Essay Interface.

4.1.10 Student Inbox

When the student clicks on the inbox section in the side navigation bar, the student is headed where the notifications are being sent in the application. As shown in Figure 12 is the interface of the inbox of the student. In the interface, it shows the notification that the application sent by the student has been approved together with the disclaimer notice that the student is not an official scholar of the agency outside of the application. The interface also shows the financial transactions of the allowance distribution. The transaction shows the transaction id, and the message that the student has received the distribution together with the amount, the name of the agency, the payment gateway used. There are two buttons, the first one is the view button where the student is able to view the receipt, and the second one is the acknowledge button where the student is able to let the donor know that the money has been received.

Figure 12. Student Inbox Interface.

4.1.11 Student Files Section

When the student clicks the credentials section in the navigation bar, they are redirected to a page where the submitted files and documents are accessed. As shown in Figure 13, the credentials section page interface is where uploaded files are located. In the interface, five documents are displayed: the grades, the certificate of enrolment, the validated school ID, the student certificate of indigency, and the tax exemption certificate. On the right side of the screen, a view action is provided to the student that opens the files when the view icon is clicked.

Documents	Action

Figure 13. Uploaded Files Interface.

4.1.12 Donor Registration Page

When the user decides to help scholarship agencies financially support students, the button at the bottom center of the login form, shown in Figure 3, allows them to create a donor account. Upon clicking the button, the user is redirected to a page where the donor account registration form is displayed. As shown in Figure 14, the form provides the user with some inputs to fill out. The donor is requested to enter personal information, including name, contact number, email address, and password. A dropdown menu for donor type is provided, allowing them to select whether the donor is anonymous, an individual, an NGO, a government, or a private company. Upon clicking the continue button, the registration process continues for verification via email. The user is then prompted that a verification code has been sent to the email used to fill out the form. A button is also provided to navigate back into the login form.

The image shows a registration form with the following fields and buttons:

- Enter Name:** Text input field with placeholder "Name of Donor".
- Select Donor Type:** Dropdown menu with "Private Companies" selected.
- Enter Contact:** Text input field with placeholder "Contact no.".
- Enter Password:** Text input field with placeholder "Password".
- Enter Email:** Text input field with placeholder "e.g Example@gmail.com".
- Confirm Password:** Text input field.
- Continue:** A green button with the text "Continue".
- Already have an account? Log in:** A green button with the text "Already have an account? Log in".

Figure 14. Donor Registration Interface.

4.1.13 Donor Profile

As shown in Figure 15, after a successful donor registration, the donor logs in to their account and is then redirected to the profile page. The interface shows the profile page for the donor account. In this interface, donors update their profile pictures and edit their personal information. The interface also displays the name of the donor, email address, and contact information.

Figure 15. Donor Profile Interface.

4.1.14 Donate Matching and List of Scholarship Agencies

When the donor clicks the donate section in the side navigation bar, they are redirected to the form where the donate feature is accessible, which they used to fill out. Donors search by entering the scholarship agency location and the minimum average requirement, then clicking the search button. Below the form is the list of the verified scholarship agencies. As shown in Figure 16, the interface shows the verified profile, agency name, and matching criteria.

The interface features two search filters at the top: "Enter Location of Agency" with a dropdown menu and "Enter Minimum Average Requirement" with a dropdown menu showing "75% - 79%". A "Search" button is positioned below these filters. A horizontal blue bar separates the search area from the results section.

The results section is titled "List of Verified Scholarship Agencies" and displays three cards:

- Tulong Dunong:** Features a logo with a graduation cap and a dollar sign, with the text "Edu Cash" below it.
- LGU:** Features a logo with a classical building and the text "LGU" above it.
- Department of Science and Technology:** Features a logo with four overlapping circles in black and blue.

Figure 16. Donate Matching Interface.

4.1.15 Searched Scholarship Agencies

After the donor enters the scholarship agency location and the minimum average requirement, the donor clicks the search button, and the scholarship agencies that meet the selected criteria are displayed. By clicking the Donate button, it proceeds to the donation process and the selection of a payment method. As shown in Figure 17, the filtered agencies appear in card format, showing the

agency name, profile picture, and two action buttons. The View button allows donors to see the list of students under the selected scholarship agency.

Figure 17. Donation Interface.

4.1.16 Payment Methods

Upon clicking the 'Donate' button on the results of the scholarship agencies displayed in the donation interface, the donor is redirected to the payment methods interface, where they proceed to make a contribution. As shown in Figure 18, the interface presents the available payment options for donors to choose from. To provide flexibility and convenience, donors select between multiple digital payment platforms, including GCash, PayPal, or Maya. This ensures that the donation process is seamless and accessible, allowing donors to complete transactions securely and efficiently. By offering various payment methods, the application accommodates the preferences of different users and encourages greater participation in supporting underprivileged yet deserving students.

Figure 18. Payment Gateways Interface.

4.1.17 Upload Receipt Form

Once the donor has decided on a preferred payment gateway, they click the corresponding button, and the page is redirected to the interface where the QR code for the selected scholarship agency is displayed. To proceed with the financial transaction, the donor first scans the QR code using the chosen payment platform and enters the donation amount. After completing the scan, the donor is required to upload the transaction receipt to finalize the donation process. By clicking the upload button, the receipt, along with the donation details, is securely sent to the scholarship agency for verification. This ensures that the agency is informed of the incoming donation and updates its records accordingly. The interface for uploading the transaction receipt, as shown in Figure 19, provides a user-friendly and straightforward process to guide the donor through each step.

Figure 19. Upload Receipt Interface.

4.1.18 Donor Inbox

Upon clicking the inbox section of the side navigation bar, the donor is then redirected to a page where the donation history is displayed. As shown in Figure 20, this is the screen layout for the donation history of donors. The donation history is displayed in a tabular format. In this interface, donors customize the donation history by scholarship agency and the month the donation was processed. In the table, the donation ID of the transaction is displayed in the first column. In the second column are the amount of the donation, followed by the name of the agency, and the date of the donation. Two dropdown filters above let donors categorize and view the total donations sent to each scholarship agency.

Donation History

All Agencies

All Months

Donation ID	Amount	Agency	Date of Donation
67	₱46,000.00	SM Foundation	May 27, 2025
68	₱46,000.00	Mcdo Agency	May 27, 2025
72	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
73	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
74	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 31, 2025
75	₱50,000.00	LGU	August 24, 2025

Total Donation: ₱292,000.00

Figure 20. Donor Donation History Interface.

4.1.19 Student List

Donation Interfaces shows a button labeled "view" that displays the list of scholars at that scholarship agency before donors decide to donate. Upon clicking, a list of scholars is displayed in a tabular format. As shown in Figure 21, a dropdown menu and a search input are provided above the list of scholars. Two buttons are also available: the filter, which is used to submit the form and filter students based on criteria from the dropdown and the search bar and the other button is the return button, which takes the donor back to the previous page. The donors categorize students by the school they are currently enrolled in and the program of study.

The screenshot shows a web interface for viewing scholars. At the top, there are two dropdown menus: 'School:' with 'All' selected and 'Program:' with 'Search program' entered. To the right of these are two buttons: a green 'Filter' button and a grey 'Return' button with a left-pointing arrow. Below the filters is a table with three columns: 'Scholar Name', 'School', and 'Program of Study'. The table contains seven rows of data, all from the University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R).

Scholar Name	School	Program of Study
Adrian Magallanes	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Zachary Guzon	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Ern Jan	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Karen Kaye Alfonso	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	BS Computer Science
Wrenz Bancolo	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing
Von Andrei Awacay	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Dorothy Abanalo	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing

Figure 21. View Scholars Interface.

4.1.20 Scholarship Agency Registration Form

In reference to the login form shown back in Figure 3, the last account type that the users are able to choose is the scholarship agency account. As shown in Figure 22 is the interface for the account registration of the scholarship agencies. The form provides five inputs for the scholarship agencies to fill out. The inputs such as the name of the scholarship agency, contact number, email address, and password together with the password confirmation. Upon clicking continue, an email is then sent to the admin that a new scholarship agency has registered an

account. Further validation and verification are processed by the admin for monitoring of the scholarship agency accounts.

The image shows a registration form for a scholarship agency. It consists of five input fields and two buttons. The fields are arranged in a grid: 'Name of Scholarship Agency' and 'Password' in the first row; 'Contact' and 'Confirm Password' in the second row; and 'Email' in the third row. Below the fields are two buttons: 'Continue' and 'Already have an Account? Login'. The 'Continue' button is green, and the 'Already have an Account? Login' button is yellow. The form is set against a light blue background with a faint watermark of a laurel wreath and the text 'Bachelor of Science in INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY'.

Figure 22. Scholarship Agency Registration Interface.

4.1.21 Scholarship Agency Profile Page

After the verification of the scholarship agency through email and by the admin, the scholarship agency is now able to access the features of the application. After a successful login, the scholarship agency is then redirected to the profile page. As shown in Figure 23, this is the screen layout for the profile page of the scholarship agency. On the profile page, the personal information of the scholarship agency is displayed, including the name, status, contact number, and email address,

along with the profile picture. Two buttons are available: the edit profile button and the button that redirects to the scholarship agency to upload the required files or certificates for validation. Below the personal information is the list of scholars for the current period.

Bacolod Agency

Email
uddinlawrence7@gmail.com

Contact:
+6309865415236

Status
Verified

[Update Photo](#) [Save](#)

[Edit Profile](#) [Upload Certificates](#)

View Scholars
University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)

Name	Program of Study	School	Files
Adrian Magallanes	Information Technology	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Zachary Guzan	Information Technology	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Ern Jan	Information Technology	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Karen Kaye Alfonso	BS Computer Science	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Wrenz Bancolo	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view

Figure 23. Scholarship Agency Profile Interface.

4.1.22 Account Not Verified Error Message

As shown in Figure 24, when the scholarship agency logs in while the account is not yet verified by the admin, an error message is prompted that the account is not yet verified. The message tells the scholarship agency to upload certificates and any necessary documents, specifically the certificate of registration and the security exchange commission certificate.

Figure 24. Account Not Verified Interface.

4.1.23 Scholarship Posting Form

After the admin fully verifies the scholarship agency, it is now able to post information and specific procedures for scholarship application, as shown in Figure 25, which is the form for scholarship posting. The form includes the setting of scholarship benefits, where the scholarship agency inputs the tuition coverage and the scholarship inclusion. Another is setting eligibility requirements, such as degree

preferences and minimum average requirements. Scholarship agencies also set the application requirements for students and the application process. Additionally, the submission and announcement of results deadlines are included in the form. The output of this process is shown in Figure 9, the feed interface.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Set Information About the Scholarship". The form is organized into four quadrants:

- Top-Left (Set Scholarship Benefits):** Includes a dropdown for "Enter Tuition Coverage" (set to "35000.00 above"), a "Scholarship Inclusion" section with multiple checkboxes (e.g., "Monthly Living Allowance", "Book and Educational Materials Allowance", etc.), and an "Other:" text input field.
- Top-Right (Set Eligibility Requirement):** Includes a "Degree Preference Related to" section with checkboxes for "Science, Technology and Mathematics", "Education", "Arts and Humanities", "Agriculture and Forestry", and "Business, Hospitality and Finance". It also has an "Other:" text input and a "Minimum Average Requirement" dropdown (set to "75% - 80%").
- Bottom-Left (Set Application Requirement):** Lists various document requirements with checkboxes, such as "Certified True Copy of Grades or Transcript of Records", "Certificate of Enrollment or Admission", "Copy of Valid School ID", "Income Tax Return (ITR) of parents/guardian", "Certificate of Indigency from Barangay or Municipality", "Latest Payslip of Parents/Guardian", "Certificate of Non-Filing of Income Tax", "Birth Certificate", "Parent's or Guardian's Valid ID", "Medical Certificate", and "Barangay Clearance or Good Moral Certificate". It also includes an "Other:" text input field.
- Bottom-Right (Set Application Process):** Features a "Set the Application Process in order" section with a list box containing "1" and a text input "Enter process 1 here". A "+" button is visible below the list box.

At the bottom of the form, there is a "Submit" button and a link: "Set a Matching Criteria? [Click Here](#)".

Figure 25. Scholarship Postings Interface.

4.1.24 Scholarship Matching Form

Before scholarship agencies manage scholarship applications, they must first set criteria for matching. This feature is accessible upon clicking the criteria

section on the side navigation bar. After clicking on the criteria section, the scholarship agency is then redirected to the page where the form for the matching criteria is displayed. As shown in Figure 26, this is the form for scholarship matching. It includes six inputs for scholarship agencies to fill out. The location of the scholarship agency, tuition coverage, minimum average requirement, application deadline, supported institutions, and coverage type are the inputs in the form. Upon clicking the "Set Criteria" button, the matching criteria are now set for students to match.

Set Criteria for Matching

Your Location	Tuition Coverage
<input type="text" value="e.g Bacolod City"/>	<input style="border: none; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;" type="text" value="below 5000.00"/>
Minimum Average Requirement	Deadline of Application
<input style="border: none; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;" type="text" value="75% - 79%"/>	<input style="border: none; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;" type="text" value="mm/dd/yyyy"/>
Supported Institutions	Coverage Type
<input style="border: none; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;" type="text" value="Private"/>	<input style="border: none; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;" type="text" value="Tuition Only"/>

Figure 26. Scholarship Matching Form Interface.

4.1.25 Scholarship Agency Inbox

When clicking inbox section on the side navigation bar, the scholarship agency is then redirected to the lists of applicants and list of donations received. As shown in Figure 27 is the inbox screen layout for scholarship agency accounts. On the first table, the pending applicants are displayed together with the name, and the date submitted. Provided with the view action where scholarship agencies are able to further validate the application process. Below the table of applicants is the table of the donations received by the scholarship agencies. Displayed are the name of the donor, date of donation, the payment method used, the amount followed by the receipt of the transaction. Provided with two actions, which is acknowledge, and to delete the transaction.

Applications					
Student Name	Date Submitted	Action			
Adrian Magallanes	2025-12-25 12:49:29				

Donations					
Donor Name	Date of Donation	Payment Method	Amount	Receipt	Action
Libertad NGO	2025-11-15 15:08:21	gcash	₱1415.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-10-31 07:50:58	gcash	₱60000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-10-15 14:54:52	gcash	₱10000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-08-24 07:37:06	gcash	₱50000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-07-24 07:33:31	gcash	₱50000.00		

Figure 27. Scholarship Agency Inbox.

4.1.26 Dashboard Interface

As shown in Figure 28, is the screen lay out for the reports and dashboard interface. When the user clicks the reports button in the sidebar section, the user is headed to the screen lay out that features the graphs and reports in the system. First is the pie chart that provides the number of each donor type such as NGO, anonymous, Government Agencies, Private Companies, and Specific Individuals, that willingly provided and supported the students that are underprivileged and deserving of the financial support. Second is the line chart for the total number of students arithmetically added each month. And lastly, is the bar graph for the total amount of donations over time each month.

Figure 28. Dashboard Interface.

4.1.27 Admin Interface

Every time a scholarship agency account is registered in the application, the admin is notified, and the admin dashboard is updated. As shown in Figure 29 are the non-verified scholarship agencies displayed in a tabular format. The table displays the name of the scholarship agency, the email address, contact number, and the status of the account. Two columns are dedicated for the certifications of the scholarship agencies with the icon indicators for missing files and if the files are uploaded and is ready to view. Also, two columns are dedicated for the action, to verify and to send an email to the scholarship agency.

Name	Email	Contact	Status	Registration CERT	SEC Certificate	Action
Kabankalan Scholarship Agency	kabankalan@gmail.com	+639895969699	Not Verified			
Himamaylan Agency	jimenez@gmail.com	+639698596633	Not Verified			
Government Service Insurance System	gsis@gmail.com	+639859632514	Not Verified			

Figure 29. Admin Interface.

4.1.28 Email Messaging Field

After clicking the envelope icon in the action column shown in Figure 30, the admin is then redirected to a field where the admin is able to fill out and write a message to the scholarship agency in the reason of following up or if the files. The documents submitted by the scholarship agency are somehow suspicious and

subjected for further verification and validation. The admin is able to send the concerns through email, and the status of the scholarship agency updates into pending state.

The screenshot displays a web interface for sending a message to the Kabankalan Scholarship Agency. At the top, there is a blue envelope icon, followed by the heading "Send Message" and the recipient "To: Kabankalan Scholarship Agency". Below this is a section titled "Message Content" with a text input area containing the placeholder text: "Write your message here... Please include any specific requirements or feedback for the agency." At the bottom right of the message area are two buttons: "← Back to Dashboard" and "Send Message". Below the message area is a section titled "Agency Information" which lists the following details:

Name: Kabankalan Scholarship Agency	Contact: +639895969699
Email: kabankalan@gmail.com	Status: Not Verified

Figure 30. Email Messaging Interface.

4.1.29 Calculation Methods

Before the scholarship agencies safely disburse the funds to the students, the scholarship agencies are able to select a calculation method on how to

distribute the funds in a calculated manner. As shown in Figure 31, is the screen interface for the calculation method. A dropdown menu is accessible for scholarship agencies to choose one from five different methods of calculation. A button is also visible to approve the method of calculation. Below the button is an overview of the calculation.

Calculation Method for AY 2025-2026 First Semester

Top 20%
▼

✔ Approve for Disbursement

Calculation for Distribution

Total Amount of Donations: ₱171415
 Total no. of Scholars: 18
 60% of Total Donations: 102,849.00
 40% of Total Donations: 68,566.00

Top 20% Scholars	Amount(60%)	Average												
Bernard Muleta	₱25 712.25	94.7												
Aliah Nicole Javier	₱25 712.25	94.7												
Andrew Batuigas	₱25 712.25	94.7												
Kent Romyr Gargalicano	₱25 712.25	94.7												
<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left;">Other Scholars</th> <th style="text-align: right;">Amount(40%)</th> <th style="text-align: right;">Average</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Gyan Warben Tamayo</td> <td style="text-align: right;">₱4 897.57</td> <td style="text-align: right;">94.63</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Bruce Wayne</td> <td style="text-align: right;">₱4 897.57</td> <td style="text-align: right;">94.63</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Jonh Lorence G. Reyes</td> <td style="text-align: right;">₱4 897.57</td> <td style="text-align: right;">94.63</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Other Scholars	Amount(40%)	Average	Gyan Warben Tamayo	₱4 897.57	94.63	Bruce Wayne	₱4 897.57	94.63	Jonh Lorence G. Reyes	₱4 897.57	94.63
Other Scholars	Amount(40%)	Average												
Gyan Warben Tamayo	₱4 897.57	94.63												
Bruce Wayne	₱4 897.57	94.63												
Jonh Lorence G. Reyes	₱4 897.57	94.63												

Figure 31. Calculation Methods Interface.

4.1.30 Allowance Distribution

After selecting a calculation method, scholarship agencies are now able to disburse the money to the students with a guide of the amount and the number of students. As shown in Figure 32, the total amount of donations and the total number of students are visible. A button with a bank icon is visible as an action that when clicked, it redirects the page to the payment gateways interface.

Calculation for Acedemic Year 2025-2026 First Semester

Total Amount of Donations: ₱171415
 Total no. of Scholars: 18
 60% of Total Donations: 102,849.00
 40% of Total Donations: 68,566.00

Top 20% Scholars	Amount(60%)	Average	Action
Bernard Muleta	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Aliah Nicole Javier	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Andrew Batuigas	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Kent Romyr Gargalicano	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Other Scholars	Amount(40%)	Average	Action
Gyan Warben Tamayo	₱4 897.57	94.63	
Bruce Wayne	₱4 897.57	94.63	
Jonh Lorence G. Reyes	₱4 897.57	94.63	
Antonio Camacho	₱4 897.57	91.5	

Figure 32. Allowance Distribution Interface.

4.2 Hardware Interfaces

The system is a web-based application and requires minimal hardware considerations. Users of the application only need a desktop computer that access a web browser and use the system. The application relies on the operating system to manage user commands and hardware interactions. Since the application is currently not compatible with mobile devices, it is optimized for desktop computers due to their larger screens, providing users with a more efficient and comfortable experience when using system features.

4.3 Software Interfaces

To carry out all intended controls and procedures in a regulated setting, the project team considered how markup, style, programming languages, terminal commands, networks, internet protocols, and modules interact with the hardware. They assessed these elements to ensure they work well together during the application execution. The project team aims to do this to identify potential issues and make the necessary adjustments to deliver a user-friendly application and an improved user experience.

4.3.1 Browser

EduCash is a web-based application that functions on any desktop computer equipped with a web browser. This includes popular search engines such as Google Chrome, Microsoft Edge, Opera, and Mozilla Firefox. The project team tested the application on these web browsers to ensure that it is compatible and has consistent functionality. Since the application is accessible, a fast, stable internet connection

is needed to enhance the user experience by improving responsiveness and reliability across different search engines and browsers. As for the different search engines, Google Chrome demonstrated its compatibility with the EduCash application, including its features and functionalities.

4.4 Communication Interfaces

The following sections identify and discuss the components and technologies involved in data transmission between the web application and the users. This includes the processes that initiate and manage data transfer, as well as those involved in financial transactions and email systems, and the processes for managing information to ensure smooth operations in the application. Additionally, the sections that follow outline the technologies used to enable the processes in the application.

4.4.1 Tesseract OCR

This engine is used for many processes in the application. By using patterns and regular expressions, the Tesseract OCR engine is a core technology behind most of the application features. This engine is used to read the documents submitted by users for validation and verification. The Tesseract OCR engine is also used to extract amounts from receipts uploaded by users for financial transactions in the application.

4.4.2 PHP Mailer

The engine is implemented in the application to securely and efficiently manage email-related functionality. It is primarily used for email notifications, such

as informing the admin when a new scholarship agency registers on the application, alerting scholarship agencies when a student submits a scholarship application, and notifying them once the donated amount has been successfully received. For email verification, PHP Mailer sends verification tokens to new users during registration to ensure only valid, active email addresses are used in the system. Additionally, PHP Mailer is integrated into the application to implement an email messaging system, allowing the admin to directly communicate with scholarship agencies regarding important matters, such as the submission of required certificates and other compliance documents.

In summary, this chapter provided a detailed discussion of the external interface requirements of the EduCash application. It explained how each feature is designed to make the system simple, organized, and easy for its users to navigate. It covered the different interfaces for students, donors, scholarship agencies, and the admin, showing how every section works together to improve the overall experience of using the application. From the login and registration pages to the upload forms, inboxes, and donation features, each part was created to make the processes faster, clearer, and more efficient for everyone involved. The chapter also discussed important technologies, such as Tesseract OCR, which helps read and validate documents, and PHP Mailer, which ensures that email notifications, verifications, and communications are sent securely and reliably. These technologies enable EduCash to safely and transparently connect donors and scholarship agencies with students while ensuring reliable applications and donations.

CHAPTER V

OTHER NONFUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

This chapter discusses the evaluation of the non-functional requirements of the EduCash Project. The evaluation focuses on the overall performance, and the quality of the system as a donation platform. The predefined criteria for software quality were used to analyze and examine the key system features and determine the top three and bottom three as the area of strength and weaknesses of the application. Additionally, the chapter also discusses the evaluation criteria interpretation, Software quality metrics and attributes, together with the feedback analysis. Moreover, the project team used ISO/IEC 25010:2011 as the quality assurance model for systems and software quality requirements and evaluation, as the application shows that it prioritizes several non-functional qualities such as security, usability, reliability and performance scalability, and maintainability and compatibility, in its system features.

5.1 Performance Requirements

This section of the paper discusses how the EduCash application performed its functionalities and features effectively and efficiently. In evaluating the performance of the application, many measures were used and implemented to solve its coefficient, which helped the project team to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the application to perform more efficiently. The software quality attributes were used to evaluate the features of the application. EduCash had four major functionalities, such as Account Creation and

Management, Scholarship Matching and Postings, Financial Transactions, and Data Analytics.

The software quality model, ISO 25010 [ISO2025], was used as reference to evaluate the system features of EduCash application in Table 12. Five leading quality attributes such as Security, Usability, Reliability, Performance Efficiency, and Maintainability, were used to examine and evaluate the feature of the application. The project team evaluated the authentication process which included the login and registration for security to ensure that the application safely keep the information of the users. The security attribute included the following criteria to be used such as confidentiality, Integrity, Accountability, and Authenticity. As for the Scholarship Matching, the quality attribute was used to evaluate its performance for the matches of student profiles and scholarship agencies. As for the financial transactions, For the Financial Transactions module, the primary quality attribute is Security, specifically focusing on Integrity, based on the ISO/IEC 25010 model. Integrity ensures that all donation and scholarship fund transactions are processed and stored without unauthorized alteration, duplication, or loss. This guarantees the correctness and trustworthiness of financial records, which is essential for maintaining donor confidence and ensuring fair distribution of scholarship funds. For the Data Analytics module of EduCash, the primary quality attribute is Accuracy, under the Functional Suitability category of ISO/IEC 25010. Accuracy ensures that the analytical output such as applicant statistics, donor contributions, scholarship demand, and matching outcomes correctly represent the underlying system data. This guarantees trustworthy insights for students, agencies, and administrators, enabling reliable decision-making based on accurate quantitative results.

System Features	Software Quality Attributes and Models	Software Quality Criteria	Mean Score	Feature Mean Score
Account Creation and Management	Security	Integrity	50%	62.5%
		Confidentiality	75%	
		Authenticity	62.5%	
Scholarship Matching and Postings	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	91.7%
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	100%	
Financial Transactions	Security	Integrity	83%	83.23%
		Confidentiality	100%	
		Authenticity	66.7%	
Calculations	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	80.6
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	66.7%	

Table 12. Summary of Features, Attributes, and Results.

As shown in Table 13, it presents the percentage ranges and their corresponding interpretations for the feature mean scores. It helps explain the derived quality scores and enables the project team to assess the performance of the system features based on its attributes. A percentage range of 84.1%-100% is marked as the highest rate a feature is able to receive, while having a 36% as the lowest rate.

Mean Score	Percentage range	Remarks
4.21-5.00	84.1% – 100%	Very Good
3.41-4.20	68.1% – 84.0%	Good
2.61-3.40	52.1% – 68.0%	Average
1.81-2.60	36.1% – 52.0%	Poor
1.00-1.80	20.0% – 36.0%	Very Poor

Table 13. Mean Score Interpretation.

5.2 Software Quality Metrics and Attributes

This section evaluates the performance of the system features are namely, security, and accuracy. These qualities are found in the software quality model ISO/IEC 25010, as shown in the Figure 33. To evaluate the functionality of the EduCash application correctly, the measures and formulas in evaluating the software quality of the system features are discussed in the appendices section of the paper with specified conditions for each software quality criteria.

Figure 33. ISO25010 Software Product Quality.

5.2.1 Integrity

The software quality attribute that ensures computer programs and data are protected from unauthorized access or modification is known as integrity. Integrity plays a critical role in maintaining the reliability and trustworthiness of a system, as it guarantees that information remains accurate, consistent, and unaltered unless performed by authorized processes or users. In the context of evaluating software systems, Formula 1 was utilized to calculate the mean integrity score, considering the relevant factors that influence this quality attribute. Specifically, the integrity percentage was determined by dividing the number of resolved requirements by the total number of requirements, thereby providing a quantitative measure of how well the system maintains its intended state against potential threats or errors.

$$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 1. Integrity Formula.

The account creation and management module of the EduCash system was evaluated using this software quality metric. The mean score from computation was 50%, indicating a moderate integrity performance. This suggests that while some requirements, such as allowing users to alter their personal information and sending email confirmations for the “forgot password” feature, were properly implemented,

other critical requirements like password confirmation during edits and administrator access to user information were not fully addressed, highlighting areas for improvement. The Financial Transactions module of the EduCash system was evaluated using this software quality metric. The mean score from computation was 83%, indicating a strong integrity performance. This signifies that most requirements, such as recording donations, updating total amounts for scholarship agencies, sending receipts to recipients, and ensuring that only scholarship agencies are able to view their received totals, were properly implemented. However, the system-generated receipts feature was not fully realized, highlighting a minor area for improvement.

5.2.2 Confidentiality

The criteria as a software quality attribute was achieved when a system ensured that data were accessible only to users with authorized access. This attribute is essential for protecting sensitive information, as it prevents unauthorized users from viewing, modifying, or exploiting confidential data. By enforcing confidentiality, the system guarantees that user credentials, personal information, and other sensitive data remain secure and anonymous, thereby maintaining trust between the system and its users. As shown in Formula 2, the evaluation of confidentiality was quantified using a formula that involved dividing the total number of confidentiality requirements by the number of resolved requirements, providing a clear metric for assessing how effectively the system met its security objectives.

$$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 2. Confidentiality Formula.

The confidentiality of the EduCash system was evaluated by examining key requirements in both the Account Creation and Management module and the Financial Transactions module. The Account Creation and Management module obtained a mean score of 75%, reflecting a good confidentiality performance, as most requirements such as user registration, verification before feature access, and email verification were properly implemented, though password hashing was not yet addressed. Meanwhile, the Financial Transactions module achieved a perfect mean score of 100%, indicating excellent confidentiality, as all requirements including protecting donor contact information, ensuring anonymity, restricting receipt visibility, and limiting access to donation history were fully satisfied. These results demonstrate that the system effectively safeguards sensitive user and financial data, with minor improvements needed in password storage practices.

5.2.3 Authenticity

The software quality attribute of authenticity was assessed using the formula presented in Formula 3, and it refers to the degree to which a user identity be verified as truly belonging to the individual claiming it. Authenticity is a critical aspect of system security, as it ensures that the information provided by users during registration such as credentials, personal details, or identification data accurately and reliably reflects their true identity. This prevents impersonation, fraudulent

access, and unauthorized use of system resources. The authenticity metric was calculated by dividing the number of resolved functions by the total number of requirements in the said criteria of the software quality, providing a quantitative measure of how effectively the system verifies and validates user identities.

$$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 3. Authenticity Formula.

The authenticity of the EduCash system was evaluated through the Account Creation and Management module and the Financial Transactions module. The Account Creation and Management module achieved a mean score of 62.5%, indicating a moderate authenticity performance. Most requirements, such as storing email and username in the database, ensuring password matches, implementing password complexity, and enabling session timeout, were fulfilled, while requirements like age restrictions, password recovery, and limiting multiple tabs were not fully addressed. The Financial Transactions module obtained a mean score of 66.7%, reflecting a slightly higher performance, with successful implementation of saving donation amounts, receipt clarity, duplicate donation prevention, and amount extraction in receipts, but leaving amount restrictions and confirmation features incomplete. These results suggest that while the system generally

maintains data authenticity, certain controls and validations need improvement to ensure complete reliability of user and financial information.

5.2.4 Correctness

The software quality attribute of correctness refers to the degree to which a system produces accurate and reliable results, as demonstrated in Formula 4. Correctness is achieved when the data and information processed by the system are accurate, and all computations, controls, and functions operate as intended. By ensuring correctness, the system not only validates the integrity of the outputs but also enhances the overall reliability and consistency of the system, leading to more dependable results. The measure of correctness was calculated by dividing the number of functions that had been successfully implemented by the total number of functions, providing a quantitative assessment of how effectively the system meets its functional requirements.

$$CR = \frac{\textit{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\textit{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 4. Correctness Formula.

The correctness of the EduCash system was evaluated through the Scholarship Matching and Postings module and the Calculation module. Both modules achieved a perfect mean score of 100%, indicating excellent correctness

performance. All critical functions, including the submit buttons for criteria and postings forms, the apply button for students, the display of error and success messages, approval buttons in calculations, enforcing one calculation per period, and the method of calculations, were implemented accurately according to the requirements specifications. These results demonstrate that the system performs its intended functions reliably and without errors, ensuring that both scholarship matching and financial calculations are executed precisely as designed.

5.2.5 Completeness

The software quality attribute of completeness reflects the degree to which the set of functions of a system satisfies all user goals and performs all specified tasks accurately and efficiently. A complete system ensures that every requirement identified during the analysis and design phases is fully addressed, leaving no critical functionality unimplemented or overlooked. Formula 5 was used to calculate the mean completeness score, which was determined by dividing the number of requirements met by the total number of requirements, providing a clear quantitative measure of system fulfillment. By assessing completeness, developers, project managers, and stakeholders are able to evaluate how thoroughly the system fulfills its intended purpose, identifying any gaps or missing features that possibly hinder user satisfaction.

$$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 5. Completeness Formula.

The completeness of the EduCash system was evaluated through the Scholarship Matching and Postings module and the Calculation module. The Scholarship Matching and Postings module achieved a mean score of 75%, indicating a good completeness performance. Most requirements, such as posting deadlines, matching students based on criteria, notifying agencies about matched students, and allowing agencies to cross-check documents, were successfully implemented, while limitations on students receiving only one scholarship and setting criteria only once were not fully addressed. Similarly, the Calculation module also obtained a mean score of 75%, reflecting that requirements like selecting a calculation method, providing an overview before approval, and informing donors were complete, while informing students about the calculation method before receiving funds remained incomplete. These results suggest that the system effectively covers the majority of its intended functionality, with minor gaps that are able to be addressed to achieve full completeness.

5.2.6 Consistency

The software quality attribute of consistency reflects the degree to which the functions of the system to behave uniformly and reliably across all modules and operations. A consistent system ensures that similar inputs produce predictable results and that processes and outputs follow the same standards and conventions throughout. Formula 6 presented how the consistency quality mean score was computed. It was calculated by dividing the number of consistent functions detected by the total number of functions described in the requirements specifications and multiplying the result by 100. By measuring consistency in this way, developers

and stakeholders evaluate how reliably the system adheres to expected behavior, reduces potential errors, and provides a stable and predictable experience for users.

$$CS = \frac{\textit{number of consistent functions detected}}{\textit{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 6. Consistency Formula.

The consistency of the EduCash system was evaluated through the scholarship matching and postings module and the calculation module. The scholarship matching and postings module achieved a perfect mean score of 100%, indicating excellent consistency performance. All functions, including aligning matches with set criteria, matching students based on averages, posting procedures and guidelines, and verifying users before access, were consistently implemented. Meanwhile, the calculation module obtained a mean score of 66.7%, reflecting moderate consistency, as most calculations were applied correctly in distributing amounts and scaling based on student numbers, but some students did not consistently receive funds according to all calculation methods. These results suggest that while the system generally maintains reliable and repeatable operations, improvements in calculation distribution consistency are needed to ensure uniform performance across all users.

5.3 Safety Requirements

The EduCash application requires users to have a desktop device for it to be accessed and for the system features to be used. In the meantime, the application only supports desktop views, since the application is currently not compatible with mobile devices. The users had to register an account and undergo certain verification processes in order to be verified and access the features. The account creation process requires users to first, select an account type, and then enter personal information and necessary documents. An email verification is sent to the email provided by the users together with the link to the application for the users to enter the verification code. Once the user is registered, and they are fully verified, the user now is able to access the features of the system. Students are able to look for scholarships and receive financial support by matching with the scholarship agencies. Scholarship agencies, after being verified by the admin, are able to set criteria for students to match, receive and disburse donations. Lastly, for donors, they are able to select a scholarship agency they want to support financially.

5.4 Testing Requirements

The developers underwent a comprehensive testing phase for the EduCash application, meticulously evaluating both technical and operational specifications to ensure that the system met all defined requirements. In this phase, the project team verified that each feature functioned as intended and accurately reflected the functionalities outlined during the design phase. This process involved systematically identifying, documenting, and resolving any discrepancies, bugs, or unexpected behaviors that affects user experience

or system performance. By thoroughly testing the application, the project team ensured that the software not only operated reliably under various conditions but also adhered to quality standards, providing users with a seamless and fully functional experience. The testing phase thus served as a critical checkpoint to validate the effectiveness, stability, and readiness of the application before its deployment.

5.4.1 Unit Testing

This activity verifies which modules conformed to the specified system requirements. In this process, users were instructed to enter only the essential information required by the EduCash application, reducing the risk of exposing personal data during account creation. Additionally, users were required to successfully complete the sign-in process in order to access all features and functionalities of the application, ensuring both security and proper system operation.

5.4.2 Integration Testing

The overall design and layout of EduCash were specifically intended for desktop use. The project focused on ensuring that the interface was optimized for larger screens, with careful consideration of the placement and size of elements to provide a clear and organized view. The front-end components were designed to be visually appealing and user-friendly, allowing users to navigate seamlessly across different desktop resolutions and window sizes. The project team also implemented a color-coded interface to avoid confusion and consolidate certain portions of the user interface, making it easier to differentiate between account types. This design choice not only improved visual clarity but also enhanced overall user experience

by allowing users to quickly identify their account sections and navigate the system more efficiently.

In summary, the evaluation of non-functional requirements of the EduCash application demonstrates that the system effectively meets key software quality standards, emphasizing security, accuracy, reliability, and usability. By using the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 model, the project team was able to systematically assess the integrity, confidentiality, authenticity, correctness, completeness, and consistency of the system features, identifying areas of strength and improvement. The desktop-focused application design, comprehensive testing procedures, and color-coded interface further ensure a secure, user-friendly, and efficient experience for students, donors, and scholarship agencies. Overall, the non-functional requirements evaluation confirms that EduCash is a reliable and robust platform that successfully supports its intended purpose of facilitating financial assistance and scholarship matching.

In addition, the evaluation highlights the capacity of system to maintain stable performance during routine operations and transaction processing. Consistent interface behavior and clear navigation contribute to improved user satisfaction across different account types. The system also demonstrates reliable response times under normal usage. These findings collectively affirm the overall quality and readiness of the EduCash application for practical deployment in an educational support environment.

CHAPTER VI

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

This chapter is important because it helps guarantee that projects are finished on schedule, within budget, and with the anticipated level of quality, project management is crucial. Additionally, it aids in risk identification and mitigation, efficient resource management, and ensuring that stakeholders are informed and involved at every stage of the project. [NU2023] this part of the paper outlines the comprehensive overview of the project. It outlines the characteristics of user classes, assessment of feasibility, the project timeline in detail, and emphasizing the technical robustness of the platform, its operational efficiency, and financial sustainability. Moreover, this part of the paper also highlights the scheduling of tasks, the resource allocation, and team composition, that aims to ensure a well-coordinated and efficient development process.

6.1 User Classes and Characteristics

The platform serves three primary user classes which includes donors, recipients, and scholarship agencies and additionally, the administrator. This section of the paper discussed the user classes and characteristics in the platform. It outlines their access to the features of the platform, and their roles for the platform to function properly.

6.1.1 Recipients

A complete list of eligible candidates comprises the primary users with access to features such as submitting grades, personal information, and family

monthly income. These requirements serve as part of the eligibility of the application process and help facilitate quicker negotiations with scholarship agencies. The financial assistance awarded by various donors such as NGOs or individual benefactors is intended for university students from poor backgrounds in the city of Bacolod.

6.1.2 Scholarship Agencies

This user class are the users who are able to directly receive the monetary donations from donors. Scholarship agencies access the platform with the functionalities such as posting information about a scholarship, provide application forms for students, and distribution of money to students once the calculation is received and once scheduled. Scholarship agencies review donation records for accuracy and accountability.

6.1.3 Donors

One of the user classes of the platform are donors. Donors include NGOs, individual donors, or anonymous donors. They are given access to various functionalities of the platform, including integrated payment gateways that make the donation process simple and secure. When making a donation, donors choose from three payment methods available on the platform, namely GCash, PayPal, and Maya, or opt for payment through bank integration. Additionally, donors have the option to categorize their donation according to the universities or colleges located in Bacolod City, allowing for more targeted support and easier tracking of contributions.

6.2 Product Feasibility

To ensure that the target user of the platform participate with the deployment of the project, the project team has analyzed and put together a strategic plan to promote the benefits of the platform and the platform itself. This section of the paper provides an overview of some aspects of feasibility assessment analysis namely the marketing, management, economic and production which are needed to achieve the objectives of the platform.

6.2.1 Marketing Feasibility

EduCash targets underprivileged college students in Bacolod City, a growing demographic facing rising educational costs. Regional universities and colleges create a strong demand for scholarships and financial aid, and EduCash provides a structured, well-managed system that ensures operational success and sustainability. The platform allows donors, NGOs, and other philanthropists to confidently channel funds directly to students in need. By addressing this critical educational access gap aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), EduCash achieves high marketability. Unlike generic crowdfunding platforms, EduCash is purpose-built for scholarship distribution, making it an attractive and secure alternative. Through secure transactions and active donor engagement, the platform encourages long-term support. Additionally, universities and scholarship agencies collaborate with EduCash to expand outreach and simplify applicant selection. The system is scalable and has potential for expansion beyond Bacolod City, increasing its overall impact. Promotional materials have been developed to support the platform, including the product packaging (see

APPENDIX M), the product poster (see APPENDIX N), and the product logo (see APPENDIX H). Moreover, the project team has added product advertisements as part of the promotional materials to enhance awareness and engagement.

6.2.2 Management Feasibility Assessment

EduCash utilizes a multidisciplinary team consisting of software developers, database administrators, UI/UX designers, and cybersecurity specialists. The development phase comprises front-end and back-end engineers who are to ensure smooth integration of the system and secure payment processing capabilities. A team of financial analysts and compliance officers oversees all transactions between donors and scholarship distributions and ensure that the platform is in compliance with the law. Others include personnel assigned to manage and serve the additional needs of software maintenance and regulation inserts usually available to secure patches and functional advancements to the system after it enters production, such as system management in relation to possible further expansion.

6.2.3 Economic Feasibility Assessment

The financial sustainability of EduCash depends on a well-structured revenue model that includes platform service fees, voluntary transaction fees, or partnerships with universities and donors. Initial funding is required for platform development, cloud hosting, cybersecurity infrastructure, and marketing efforts. A break-even analysis helps determine when the platform sustains itself based on projected donation volumes and user engagement. The cost of integrating secure payment gateways like PayPal, GCash, and Maya must be factored into operational

expenses. Potential grants from educational and philanthropic organizations help subsidize early-stage development costs. A subscription or commission-based model for scholarship agencies provides additional revenue streams without burdening student beneficiaries. Long-term financial projections should include system upgrades, customer support scaling, and expansion plans to other cities. Efficient resource allocation and budgeting are crucial to ensuring the financial viability of the platform.

6.2.4 Production Feasibility Assessment

Since EduCash is a web-based application, its production feasibility relies primarily on software development rather than physical manufacturing. The platform must be built using scalable cloud-based infrastructure to accommodate a growing number of users and increasing transaction volumes, always ensuring smooth performance. By hosting the system on secure servers with robust data encryption and backup measures, compliance with financial and privacy regulations while protecting sensitive user information is guaranteed. The distribution of EduCash primarily occurs through digital marketing campaigns, university partnerships, and social media outreach to reach potential students, donors, and scholarship agencies. A mobile-responsive design enhances accessibility, allowing users to interact with the platform via smartphones, tablets, and computers. Prior to full launch, thorough system testing and collection of user feedback are crucial steps to ensure platform reliability, usability, and overall user satisfaction. Regular updates, performance monitoring, and feature enhancements maintain platform competitiveness and allow adaptation to evolving user needs.

6.3 Time Management

This section of the paper, the project team provides an overview of the effective time management is essential for the successful development and deployment of EduCash. This aims to ensure that the project meets its objectives within the proposed timeline, the time management plan has been broken down into phases with clear milestones and deadlines. The subsequent section of this paper provides the project time overview of the project, which is composed of planning, research, design and prototype development, platform development, and testing.

6.3.1 Project Timeline Overview

This section provides a high-level overview of the project timeline, detailing the sequence of activities from initial planning to final deployment. Each phase has an estimated time frame, carefully determined by considering task priorities, the availability of resources, and the complexity of technical requirements. This structured timeline ensures that the project progresses efficiently while allowing for proper allocation of effort and monitoring of milestones.

6.3.1.1 Planning and Research

In the initial phase, the focus is on conducting thorough research and gathering all necessary requirements to establish a solid foundation for EduCash. This includes studying existing platforms, understanding the needs of target users (both donors and students), and assessing technical and financial feasibility. Additionally, project planning activities, such as defining goals, setting up the project scope, and creating a detailed project

roadmap, are completed to ensure all stakeholders have a clear vision of the objectives of the project.

6.3.1.2 Design and Prototype Development

In this phase of design and the development of the prototypes of the project, the project team designs the user interface (UI) and develops a prototype to showcase core functionalities of EduCash platform. The design focuses on an intuitive and user-friendly interface that appeals to both students and donors. The prototyping phase allows stakeholders to visualize the platform early, providing feedback on navigation, visual elements, and essential features, helping refine the design to meet user expectations before the main development begins. Moreover, the project team utilizes Figma for the design of the prototypes.

6.3.1.3 Platform Development

The development of the platform is the most intensive phase, encompassing coding, backend development, payment gateway integration, and database setup. This phase involves building the core functionalities of the system, including user authentication, secure payment processing, and data storage with high encryption standards to protect sensitive information. Integration of multiple payment options, such as PayPal, GCash, and Maya, ensures convenient and flexible donation methods for users. At the same time, backend programming establishes reliable data management for student applications, donor information, and transaction tracking, supporting accurate and efficient operations.

6.3.1.4 Testing and Quality Assurance

To ensure platform stability and security, comprehensive testing is conducted to address any bugs or usability issues. This phase includes unit testing, integration testing, and system testing to verify each function works correctly and efficiently. Usability testing sessions are held with a select group of users to gain feedback on navigation and ease of use, while security and performance tests are conducted to validate data protection measures and platform responsiveness under varying loads.

6.4 Task Scheduling and Priority

Tasks are prioritized to ensure that essential features, like payment integration and security measures, are completed early in the development process. High-priority tasks are essential to the functionality of the platform, while medium and low-priority tasks enhance usability and visual appeal. This scheduling approach helps manage workload efficiently, focusing team efforts on tasks that are crucial for the initial success of the platform.

6.5 Resource Allocation

Efficient resource allocation is achieved by assigning specific roles and responsibilities to team members based on skill sets. Essential resources include technical tools, project management software, and partnerships with financial institutions. Proper resource planning ensures that all development and integration needs are met without straining the timeline or budget.

6.6 Communication, Coordination, and Team Composition

For EduCash, effective communication, coordinated teamwork, and a well-defined team composition are essential to ensure successful project execution. The following subsections outline the structure used to maintain alignment and collaboration among team members. Regular meetings and updates help keep all members informed of progress and challenges. Task assignments are clearly defined to avoid overlap, ensure accountability, and allow team members to focus on their specific responsibilities efficiently.

6.6.1 Communication

To facilitate seamless communication, the team uses platforms such as Microsoft Teams and Discord for real-time messaging and calls. These tools allow team members to share updates, address concerns, and conduct meetings remotely. By using multiple communication channels, the team ensures timely collaboration and efficient project coordination.

6.6.2 Coordination

Task assignments and progress tracking are managed through Google Docs, which provides a centralized space for documenting updates, making revisions, and sharing project-related files among team members. For version control and collaboration, GitHub is used to store and manage code changes, enabling the team to track revisions, integrate updates efficiently, and maintain a reliable history of development progress. This combination of tools ensures that all team members stay aligned, deadlines are met, and the project progresses smoothly without miscommunication.

6.6.3 Team Composition

The EduCash project team consists of three dedicated members, each fulfilling distinct roles that collectively contribute to the successful development of the platform. This small but specialized team enables clear communication, effective collaboration, and efficient task distribution. By working closely together, the team address challenges promptly, coordinate development activities smoothly, and ensure that each aspect of the platform meets the desired quality and functionality standards.

6.6.3.1 Project Manager

Oversees the project timeline, sets milestones, and manages the allocation of resources to ensure smooth project flow. Responsibilities include scheduling weekly meetings, coordinating between frontend and backend development, and maintaining alignment with project goals and requirements. By tracking progress and managing timelines, the Project Manager ensures that the platform development stays on course, addressing any issues promptly to keep the project on track. Project Manager also serves as paper writer in the team. The project manager is also the one responsible for the documentation of the project.

6.6.3.2 Front-end Developer

The developer for the system design is responsible for building and styling the user interface of the EduCash platform, focusing on both functionality and visual appeal. With the use of HTML for structure, CSS for styling, BOOTSTRAP 5 for responsiveness, and JavaScript for

interactive elements, they create an intuitive and responsive layout that ensures accessibility across various devices and screen sizes. Their role involves developing features that allow users to navigate smoothly, access information, and complete transactions with ease. The Front-End Developer collaborates with the Back-End Developer to integrate data securely and accurately, ensuring a cohesive experience for users from login to final transaction.

6.6.3.3 Backend Developer

The developer for logic formulation handles server-side programming, database management, and the integration of essential features such as user authentication, document verification, and payment gateway functionality. Their role involves developing a secure, efficient backend system using frameworks like Django and managing data flow between the server and the client-side. They collaborate with the Front-End Developer to ensure data is processed and displayed accurately, and with the Project Manager to prioritize backend tasks essential to the core operations of the platform.

In summary, this chapter of the paper comprehensively described the process of managing the project, discussing the essential stages ranging from identifying user classes to conducting a thorough feasibility assessment and assembling a competent team composition. Each of these components is not merely a procedural formality but represents

a critical pillar that supports the overall success of the project. The identification of user classes, for instance, serves as a vital precursor to understanding the diverse needs and expectations of potential end-users, thereby allowing project managers to develop strategies and approaches that address these specific requirements effectively. Similarly, the feasibility assessment provides a structured framework for evaluating the technical, economic, and operational viability of the project, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently, timelines are maintained, and potential risks are proactively identified and mitigated. Moreover, assembling a well-balanced team with clearly defined roles and complementary skills enhances collaboration, accelerates problem-solving, fosters a productive working environment, and promotes accountability among team members. The integration of communication tools, task management platforms, and version control systems further strengthens coordination, transparency, and consistency throughout the development process. By meticulously addressing these foundational elements, the project establishes a strong groundwork that improves the likelihood of achieving its objectives while maintaining high standards of quality, operational efficiency, and stakeholder satisfaction. Furthermore, the deliberate attention to planning, monitoring, and evaluation underscores the importance of strategic foresight and informed decision-making, guiding the project through complex challenges and ensuring that each stage aligns with its intended goals. Ultimately, the careful integration of these comprehensive management practices demonstrates the pivotal role of structured organization, team synergy, and methodical execution in steering the project toward successful implementation.

CHAPTER VII

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter discussed the summary and the recommendations of the EduCash application. A web-based application designed to support college students in studying in Bacolod City that struggles financially but at the same time excels in their academic performance, providing them financial support and academic opportunities, and to promote the act of giving by targeting multiple donors such as NGO, private agencies, government organizations, individual donors, and anonymous donors. This chapter discusses the comprehensive summary of the system features, interfaces, and other functionalities that provides overview of the development of the application and its purpose.

7.1 Summary

EduCash is a web-based application designed to support underprivileged and deserving college students in Bacolod City. This system connects students with individual donors, NGOs, and government agencies to facilitate financial assistance for education. Users must create accounts to access features like scholarship matching, which pairs students with suitable agencies based on academic performance. A document verification module ensures the authenticity of student credentials to prevent fraudulent applications. Donors utilize a dedicated portal to send funds and track their donation history through generated receipts. The application integrates payment gateways such as PayPal, GCash, and Maya for secure monetary transactions. Scholarship agencies manage the disbursement

of funds to students using specific calculation methods provided by the platform. The interface uses color-coded backgrounds to help users differentiate between various account types easily. Data analytics features offer visual reports on donation trends and student performance for administrative monitoring. This project aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal for Quality Education by bridging financial gaps for students.

7.2 Recommendation

EduCash is a web-based application designed to provide financial support to underprivileged and deserving college students in Bacolod City. The platform fosters social solidarity by connecting students with individual donors, NGOs, and government agencies eager to fund education. As users start on their journey with EduCash, the application serves its purpose by bridging the gap between financial needs and educational opportunities. The system provides students the knowledge about available scholarships through a centralized space for fast inquiries. Users explore and choose specific scholarship agencies or receive matches based on their academic credentials and performance. The application then provides the steps for document verification to ensure only qualified applicants access financial aid. A dedicated donor portal allows benefactors to send funds securely and track their donation history through generated receipts. The application is designed with a color-coded interface to offer a seamless and organized navigation experience for various account types. Data analytics features offer visual reports on donation trends and student performance to evaluate platform impact. Overall, EduCash

seeks to create an inclusive and transparent platform that promotes academic excellence and long-term social change.

7.2.1 System Generated Receipt

One of the critical recommendations from the panel review is the implementation of an automated system-generated receipt feature that consolidates and standardizes transaction documentation across all payment gateways integrated within the EduCash platform. Currently, the application relies on manual receipt uploads from donors and scholarship agencies after completing transactions through GCash, Maya, or PayPal, which introduces several operational inefficiencies and potential risks including inconsistent documentation formats, difficulty in verification and audit trails, potential for fraudulent or altered receipts, and increased administrative overhead for manual validation. To address these limitations, the proposed system-generated receipt feature leverages the existing Tesseract OCR engine to automatically extract critical transaction information from uploaded payment gateway receipts, including transaction ID, amount, date and time stamps, sender and recipient details, and payment method identifiers. This extracted data then undergoes validation against the donation records in the database to ensure accuracy and prevent duplicate submissions. Upon successful validation, the system automatically generates a standardized, official EduCash receipt in PDF format that incorporates the platform branding, includes a unique system-generated receipt number for tracking and reference purposes, and contains a QR code linking to the verified transaction record for authenticity verification. The generated receipt is simultaneously distributed to all relevant parties through

automated email notifications sent to the donor with their official tax-deductible receipt, transmitted to the scholarship agency for their financial records and acknowledgment, and archived in the system database with encrypted storage for compliance and audit purposes. This implementation significantly enhances the platform credibility and professionalism, streamlines the donation acknowledgment process, reduces administrative workload, provides donors with immediate standardized documentation for tax purposes, creates a comprehensive audit trail for financial accountability and transparency, and ensures compliance with financial reporting requirements for both donors and scholarship agencies. The expected benefits of this implementation include an estimated 75% reduction in receipt processing time, a projected 90% decrease in receipt-related disputes and clarification requests, enhanced donor satisfaction through immediate receipt generation and professional documentation, improved compliance with financial regulations and audit requirements, and strengthened platform credibility through standardized, tamper-proof transaction records.

7.2.2 Fully Integrated Payment Gateways

A significant recommendation from the panel review is the complete integration of payment gateways including GCash, PayPal, and Maya directly into the EduCash platform to enable seamless, real-time transaction processing without requiring users to leave the application interface. The current implementation presents a semi-manual approach where donors select their preferred payment method, navigate to external platforms to complete transactions, and then return to EduCash to manually upload transaction receipts as proof of payment. This

fragmented workflow creates multiple pain points including interrupted user experience that increases transaction abandonment rates, delayed confirmation of donations, increased opportunity for human error in amount entry and receipt upload, administrative burden of manually verifying each uploaded receipt, and lack of real-time financial tracking capabilities. The proposed full integration addresses these issues by embedding the payment gateway APIs directly into the EduCash transaction flow through establishing direct connections with GCash Developer API[DA2022], PayPal REST API, and Maya Checkout API[MC2022]. Upon successful payment completion, the integrated system receives immediate transaction confirmations through webhook callbacks that automatically trigger backend processes including database recording, receipt generation, and stakeholder notifications. This implementation transforms the donation process from a fragmented workflow requiring several minutes and manual verification into a streamlined experience completable within seconds.

7.2.3 One student, One Scholarship Agency

A critical recommendation from the panel review is the implementation of a strict one student, one scholarship agency policy to ensure fair distribution of financial resources and prevent scholarship hoarding by individual students. The current system allows students to apply to and potentially receive financial support from multiple scholarship agencies simultaneously, creating issues including unequal distribution of limited scholarship funds, administrative complications in tracking and disbursing funds, potential ethical concerns regarding fairness, and reduced overall platform impact by concentrating resources on fewer beneficiaries

rather than maximizing the number of students helped. The proposed policy enforces a single active scholarship match per student through database constraints and application logic that automatically prevents students from applying to additional agencies once they have been accepted by one scholarship provider, with the student account status changing to "actively enrolled" and all other pending applications automatically withdrawn with notifications sent to both the student and the affected agencies. This restriction remains in effect until the student either completes their program, fails to maintain the required academic standards and is dropped from the scholarship, or the scholarship agency terminates the arrangement, at which point the student regains eligibility to match with a different agency. The implementation provides clear benefits including equitable distribution of scholarship resources across a larger number of deserving students, simplified financial tracking and disbursement processes, reduced administrative overhead, enhanced transparency and fairness in the allocation system, prevention of potential abuse or manipulation, and increased overall social impact by maximizing the total number of students receiving educational support through the application.

EduCash is a web-based platform that connects underprivileged college students in Bacolod City with donors, NGOs, and government agencies to provide financial support and promote academic opportunities. The system features scholarship matching, document verification, donor portals, secure payment integrations, color-coded interfaces, and data

analytics to ensure transparency, efficiency, and impact monitoring. Key recommendations include implementing automated system-generated receipts, fully integrating payment gateways for seamless transactions, and enforcing a “one student, one scholarship agency” policy to ensure fair resource distribution. These enhancements aim to streamline operations, improve user experience, strengthen accountability, and maximize the social and educational impact application. In addition, the automated receipt feature reduces processing time, minimize disputes, and provide standardized, tamper-proof documentation for donors and scholarship agencies. Full payment gateway integration enables real-time transactions, immediate confirmation, and lower the risk of human error, creating a smoother donation experience. The one student, one scholarship agency policy ensures equitable distribution of funds, prevents scholarship hoarding, and increases the total number of beneficiaries supported by the platform. Overall, these improvements enhance credibility, operational efficiency, and alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal of Quality Education. Through these strategic enhancements, EduCash positions itself as a sustainable, scalable, and socially responsible digital solution that strengthens multi-sector collaboration and advances inclusive access to higher education in Bacolod City.

GLOSSARY

A. ACCOUNT CREATION AND MANAGEMENT

A feature of EduCash that allows the users to create and manage their personal account, that provides users a personalized access in the platform.

B. ALLOWANCE DISTRIBUTION

A feature of EduCash that grants students the financial support that they deserved from donors.

C. ANONYMOUS

Refers to the donors of EduCash who is likely rather not want to share their Identity to other users of EduCash.

D. CALCULATED CASH ASSISTANCE

A purpose of EduCash that is defined to provide the students calculated cash assistance from the monetary donations that are gathered from NGO, individual, and anonymous donors.

E. DATA ANALYTICS

A feature of EduCash that provides users the analytics of the total amount that is donated in the platform, the total number of applicants, the total number of NGO donated, and the pie chart of specific and anonymous individuals and other data visualization such as bar graphs.

F. DATA VALIDATION/DOCUMENT VERIFICATION

A criterion and a feature of EduCash that validates and verifies the data that is being sent or submitted into the platform.

G. DONOR PORTAL/DONOR PROFILE

A criterion of EduCash that refers to the personalized space of donors in the platform.

H. EDUCASH

A platform that aims to connect donors and underprivileged and deserving college students that are studying in Bacolod City.

I. MONETARY DONATIONS

It refers to one of the scopes of the platform that means the donations are only accepted is in a form of money.

J. NON-GOVERNMENT ORGANIZATIONS

An actor of EduCash that provides financial support to students through monetary donations using payment gateways.

K. PAYMENT GATEWAYS

A criterion of EduCash that refers to the means of financial transactions in the platform, examples are PayPal, Gcash, Maya, and Bank Payment Integration.

L. SCHOLARSHIP AGENCIES

An actor of EduCash who receives the donations before distributing it to the students and providing students educational opportunities.

M. SCHOLARSHIP MATCH

A feature of EduCash that allows students to match their credentials to scholarship agencies and provide them an application form.

N. SECURITY MEASURES

A criterion of EduCash that is employed to protect sensitive data and the privacy of students, also safeguarding transactions from one server to another.

O. UNDERPRIVILEGED AND DESERVING COLLEGE STUDENTS

An actor of EduCash that receives the calculated monetary donations from donor as financial support for their education.

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USERS' MANUAL

This section provides users with step-by-step guidance on how to navigate and use the different modules of the application. It includes screenshots of the system interface accompanied by clear descriptions to help users better understand how the web application functions. The manual consists of detailed explanations of text fields, buttons, dropdown menus, and other interface elements to support ease of use. The application accessed through its official website, educash.com, and for optimal performance, a stable internet connection with a minimum speed of 25 Mb/s is recommended.

1. Login Page

EduCash is open to all users who wish to use the application. For those who already have an account, logging in is quick and seamless. The user simply enters their registered credentials to access the system and explore its features. As shown in Screenshot 1, the login interface and serves as a guide for the required inputs.

Screenshot 1. EduCash Login Interface.

- A. Email Text Field – A text field provided for the users to type their registered user credentials.
- B. Password Text Field – A text field where users input the password associated with their account.
- C. Remember me Checkbox – A checkbox that allows the system to remember the user login credentials, making future logins faster without requiring the user to re-enter their information.
- D. Eye Shaped Icon – An icon that users toggle to show or hide the password entered in the password field.
- E. Forgot Password Link – A link that redirects users to the forgot password interface, allowing them to securely reset their password, recover account access, and continue using the application without interruption.
- F. Sign In Button – A button that users click after completing the required fields to log in to their account.
- G. Create Student Account Button – A button provided for users who wish to register as a student and do not yet have an account.
- H. Create Donor Account Button – A button intended for individuals, organizations, or entities who wish to register as donors and gain access to donation features within the application.
- I. Create Agency Account Button – A button used by scholarship agencies to register and create an official agency account, providing access to all system features and management tools.

2. Forgot Password

As shown in Screenshot 2, the application provides a user-friendly “Forgot Password” interface for users who have forgotten their account credentials. Through this feature, users enter their registered email address to initiate the password recovery process. Once the Send Password Reset Link button is selected, the system automatically sends a reset link to the provided email address, directing users to a dedicated interface for securely resetting their password.

Screenshot 2. Forgot Password Interface.

- A. Email Text Field - A text field where users enter their registered email address to receive a verification code for password recovery.
- B. Send Code Button – A button that sends a verification code to the email address provided by the user.
- C. Verify It Button – A button that confirms the entered email address and proceeds to the next step of the password recovery process.
- D. Back to Sign in Link – A link that redirects the user back to the sign-in page of the application.
- E. Code Text Field – A text field where users input the verification code sent to their email address.
- F. Verify Code Button – A button that validates the entered verification code and allows the user to continue with resetting their password.
- G. Resend Code Link – A link that allows users to request a new verification code if the previous one has expired or was not received.
- H. Back to Sign in Link – A link that returns the user to the login page at any point during the verification process.

3. Verification Code

As shown in Screenshot 3, the application displays the verification code for users. This code is used to confirm the identity of the user during account verification or password recovery. Users simply view the code and proceed to the next step in the process.

Screenshot 3. Verification Code.

4. Student Registration Page

As shown in Screenshot 4, the Student Registration Page allows new users to easily create a student account within the application. This page provides clearly labeled input fields where students enter their personal and academic information, such as full name, school, program, and contact details. The registration process is simple and user friendly, guiding students through each required step and providing prompts or instructions to ensure all information is entered accurately. The system also performs basic validation to check for errors or missing information, helping prevent incomplete submissions. Once the registration is completed successfully, students are granted access to the systems functionalities, enabling them to utilize features such as scholarship applications, document uploads, and tracking of donation distributions.

Create a Student Account

<input type="text" value="Full Name"/> ← A	<input type="text" value="Search School"/> ← E
<input type="text" value="Contact."/> ← B	<input type="text" value="Search Program"/> ← F
<input type="text" value="Email"/> ← C	<input type="text" value="mm/dd/yyyy"/> ← G
<input type="text" value="Password"/> ← D	<input type="text" value="Confirm Password"/> ← H

I →

← **J**

Screenshot 4. Student Registration Interface.

- A. Full Name – A text field where users enter their complete legal name for account registration.
- B. Contact – A text field where users provide their active contact number for communication purposes.
- C. Email – A text field where users input a valid email address to be used as their login credential and for account verification.
- D. Password – A text field where users create a secure password for their account.
- E. Search School – A search field that allows users to find and select the educational institution where they are currently enrolled.
- F. Select Program – A dropdown menu where users choose their current program or course of study.
- G. Select Birthday – A date selector that allows users to choose their date of birth.

- H. Confirm Password – A text field where users re-enter their password to prevent errors.
- I. Continue Button – A button that submits the entered information and proceeds to the next step of the registration process.
- J. Already Have an Account – A link that redirects users back to the sign-in page if they already have an existing account.

5. Upload Credentials Form

As shown in Screenshot 5, The Upload Credentials Interface provides students with a structured way to submit the required documents for verification. Each upload field is clearly labeled to help users attach the correct files without confusion. The interface guides students through the process step by step, ensuring that all required documents are completed before submission. Once the documents are uploaded, students submit their credentials for review and validation by the system.

The screenshot shows a form titled "Upload Credentials" with the following elements:

- A**: Upload certified true copy of grades (Icon: Graduation cap)
- B**: Upload certificate of enrolment (Icon: Document)
- C**: Upload validated school ID (Icon: ID card)
- D**: Upload Certificate of Indigency (Icon: House)
- E**: Upload Proof of Income (Icon: Document with dollar sign)
- F**: Submit button (Icon: Arrow pointing left)

Screenshot 5. Upload Credentials Interface.

- A. Upload Certified True Copy of Grades – A file upload field where students submit an official and certified copy of their academic grades for verification.
- B. Upload Certificate of Enrollment – A file upload field used to submit proof that the student is currently enrolled in an educational institution.
- C. Upload Validated School ID – A file upload field where students upload a valid school identification card to confirm their student status.
- D. Upload Certificate of Indigency – A file upload field for submitting an official document that certifies the financial need of student.
- E. Upload Proof of Income – A file upload field where students provide documents showing the income of their parent or guardian for financial assessment.
- F. Submit Button – A button that submits all uploaded documents for system validation and review.

6. Student Profile

As shown in Screenshot 6, Student Profile Interface provides students with a convenient space to manage and update their personal information within the application. Through this interface, students upload or edit their profile photo, allowing them to personalize their account. It also includes options for updating credentials, where students submit or modify required documents such as proof of income for verification. Changes made in the profile saved using the submit button to ensure that updated information is properly applied.

Screenshot 6. Student Profile Interface.

- A. Upload Photo – A file upload option that allows users to add or change their profile photo within the application.
- B. Submit Button – A button used to save and apply the uploaded photo or updated information.
- C. Update Credentials Button – A button that redirects users to the credentials page, that allows students to upload or modify required documents.
- D. Edit Photo Button – A button that allows users to replace or update their existing profile photo.
- E. Upload Proof of Income – A file upload field where users submit an updated proof of income document for verification purposes.

7. Matched Scholarships

As shown Screenshot 7, The Matched Scholarships Interface serves as a results page where students are presented with scholarship opportunities generated by the system based on their submitted credentials. This interface automatically filters available scholarships using eligibility criteria such as academic standing, financial need, and personal background. Students view all scholarships that match their credentials in one consolidated list.

Screenshot 7. Matched Scholarships Interface.

A. Apply now - A button that allows users to start the scholarship application process.

8. Application Form

As shown in Screenshot 8, application essay interface provides a form for students to fill out and submit to the scholarship agency. The application form provides a question to the student of why is that student deserve the scholarship. To guide the students of the

number of words that is currently being typed, a word counter below at the bottom right side of the text-area is provided.

Why do you deserve this Scholarship? (Please write a minimum of 200 words)

I believe I deserve this scholarship because I am committed to achieving academic excellence while using my education to create meaningful impact in my community. Throughout my academic journey, I have consistently demonstrated dedication, perseverance, and a strong work ethic, even in the face of financial challenges. My passion for learning drives me to continuously improve myself, not only for personal success but also to contribute to the betterment of society.

Receiving this scholarship would greatly ease my financial burden, allowing me to focus more on my studies and participate in academic and community initiatives that foster growth and development. I plan to use my knowledge and skills to help address pressing issues in my community, such as improving access to education and creating opportunities for underprivileged youth.

This scholarship represents more than just financial assistance; it is an opportunity to further develop my potential, enhance my leadership abilities, and give back to those who have supported me along the way. I am determined to maximize this opportunity and uphold the values of hard work, responsibility, and service. With your support, I can continue striving toward my academic goals and become a positive force for change. Thank you and God Bless!

Words: 201

Submit Application

Screenshot 8. Application Essay Interface.

- A. Essay Form Text field – A text field that allows student to input their scholarship essay.
- B. Submit Application – A button that allows the student to send their completed scholarship application and essay to the scholarship agency for review.

9. Student Inbox

As shown in Screenshot 9, the Student Inbox interface provides students with notifications regarding the status of their applications, including approval messages from

the application. Each notification is accompanied by a disclaimer clarifying that the student is not considered an official scholar of the agency outside of the application. In addition to application updates, the interface displays detailed financial transactions related to allowance distribution. Each transaction includes the transaction ID, a message confirming that the student has received the distribution, the amount received, the name of the agency, and the payment gateway used. This comprehensive overview allows students to easily track their financial support, verify the sources of donations, and maintain transparency in their scholarship-related transactions.

Screenshot 9. Student Inbox Interface.

- A. Acknowledge – A button that allows students to let the donor know that the money has been received.

B. View – A button that allows student to view the receipt of the transaction.

10. Student Files Section

As shown in Screenshot 10, Student Files Section interface provides students the credentials section page where uploaded files are located. In the interface, there are five documents that are shown namely the grades, the certificate of enrolment, the validated school ID, the certificate of indigency of the student, together with the tax exemption certificate. These documents are used for verification and validation purposes within the system.

Your Uploaded Files			
Documents			Action

Screenshot 10. Uploaded Files Interface.

A. View Grades – A button to view the transcript or report card.

- B. View Certificate of Enrollment - A button that allows to view the official document proving current enrollment.
- C. View School ID - A button that allows to view the valid student card.
- D. View Certificate of Indigency - A button that allows to view the document certifying financial status.
- E. View Certificate of Tax Exemption - A button that allows to view the official document indicating any tax exemptions.

11. Donor Registration Page

As shown in Screenshot 11, The Donor Registration Page allows new users to easily create a donor account within the application. This page provides clearly labeled input fields where Donors enters their name, contact number, email address, and password. A dropdown menu for donor type is provided where they are able to decide whether anonymous, individual, NGO, government, or private companies for the donor type.

The screenshot displays a registration form with the following elements:

- Enter Name:** A text input field with the placeholder "Name of Donor". An arrow labeled **A** points to this field.
- Select Donor Type:** A dropdown menu with "Private Companies" selected. An arrow labeled **D** points to this menu.
- Enter Contact:** A text input field with the placeholder "Contact no.". An arrow labeled **B** points to this field.
- Enter Password:** A text input field with the placeholder "Password". An arrow labeled **E** points to this field.
- Enter Email:** A text input field with the placeholder "e.g Example@gmail.com". An arrow labeled **C** points to this field.
- Confirm Password:** A text input field.
- Continue:** A green button. An arrow labeled **G** points to this button.
- Already have an account? Log in:** A green button. An arrow labeled **H** points to this button.
- F:** A label positioned near the bottom right of the form area.

Screenshot 11. Donor Registration Interface.

- A. Name – A text field where donors enter their complete legal name for account registration.
- B. Contact – A text field where donors provide their active contact number for communication purposes.
- C. Email – A text field where donors input a valid email address to be used as their login credential and for account verification.
- D. Select Donor Type – A dropdown A dropdown field where donor choose whether anonymous, individual, NGO, government, or private companies.
- E. Password – A text field where donors create a secure password for their account.
- F. Confirm Password – A text field where users re-enter their password to prevent errors.
- G. Continue - A button that submits the entered information and proceeds to the next step of the registration process.
- H. Already Have an Account – A link that redirects users back to the sign-in page if they already have an existing account.

12. Donor Navigation Bar

As shown in Screenshot 12, Primary donor interface, serving as the central hub for donors. In this interface donors manage their account and access key features of the application. It allows donors to view and edit their profile information, make donations, check reports, and communicate through the inbox. Navigation options are clearly displayed to help users move between different sections efficiently. The interface also

provides tools for updating profile details, including uploading a profile photo and saving changes.

Screenshot 12. Donor Navigation Bar Interface.

- A. Profile – A navigation option that allows donors to view and manage their personal account information.
- B. Donate – A navigation button that redirects donors to the donation page, where they contribute funds to selected beneficiaries or programs.
- C. Reports – A section where donors view records and summaries of their donation activities.
- D. Inbox - A messaging feature that allows donors to receive updates, notifications, and messages within the application.

- E. Upload Photo - A file upload option that allows donors to add or change their profile photo.
- F. Save Button - A button used to save and apply any changes made to the profile information of donor.
- G. Edit Profile - A button that enables donors to modify their personal details and update profile information.

13. Donate Matching

As shown in Screenshot 13, the application provides donors with a search function to find scholarship agencies. Donors enter the location of the scholarship agency and specify the minimum average requirement for applicants. After filling out these details, they can click the search button to view matching scholarship agencies.

The screenshot displays a search interface for finding scholarship agencies. At the top, there are two dropdown menus: 'Enter Location of Agency' (labeled A) and 'Enter Minimum Average Requirement' (labeled B, showing '75% - 79%'). A 'Search' button (labeled C) is located below the dropdowns. Below the search form is a section titled 'List of Verified Scholarship Agencies' containing three agency cards: 'EduCash' (Tulong Dunong), 'LGU', and 'Department of Science and Technology'.

Screenshot 13. Donate Matching Interface.

- A. Enter Location of Agency – A text field where donors input the location of the scholarship agency to narrow down search results.
- B. Enter Average Requirement – A dropdown field where donors the select minimum average grade requirement set by the scholarship agency.
- C. Search Button - A button that initiates the search process and displays scholarship agencies that match the entered criteria.

14. Searched Scholarship Agencies

As shown in Screenshot 14, the filtered scholarship agencies are displayed in a card-based layout for easy viewing. Each card presents the name of the scholarship agency along with its profile picture to help donors identify the organization. The interface provides action buttons that allow donors to interact with each scholarship agency. By selecting the appropriate option, donors either view additional details or proceed with the donation process.

Screenshot 14. Donation Interface.

- A. View Button – A button that displays the list of students associated with the selected scholarship agency.
- B. Donate Button – A button that allows donors to proceed with the donation process for the selected scholarship agency.

15. Payment Methods

As shown in Screenshot 15, the application provides a payment gateway that allows donors to complete their donations using available digital payment methods. This interface displays the supported payment options, enabling donors to select their preferred method and proceed with the transaction securely. Once a payment option is chosen, the system guides the donor through the necessary steps to successfully complete the donation process.

Screenshot 15. Payment Gateways Interface.

- A. Gcash button– A payment option that allows donors to complete their donation using the GCash e-wallet.
- B. Paypal button – A payment option that enables donors to donate securely through their PayPal account.
- C. Maya button – A payment option that allows donors to make donations using the Maya digital wallet.

16. Upload Receipt Form

As shown in Screenshot 16, the application provides donors with an interface for uploading the transaction receipt after completing the payment. This interface allows donors to submit proof of payment to confirm that the donation has been successfully made. Once the receipt is uploaded, the system sends the transaction details to the selected scholarship agency for verification.

Screenshot 16. Upload Receipt Interface.

- A. Choose File button - A button that allows donors to select and attach the payment receipt for upload.
- B. Upload Receipt button - A button that allows donors to submit the payment receipt to complete and confirm the donation transaction.

17. Donor Inbox

As shown in Screenshot 17, This interface displays a complete record of all donations made by the donor through the application. The donation history is presented in a tabular format. Above the table, two dropdown filter options are provided. These filters allow the donor to customize the displayed donation records based on the selected scholarship agency and the month of donation.

Donation ID	Amount	Agency	Date of Donation
67	₱46,000.00	SM Foundation	May 27, 2025
68	₱46,000.00	Mcdo Agency	May 27, 2025
72	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
73	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
74	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 31, 2025
75	₱50,000.00	LGU	August 24, 2025

Total Donation: ₱292,000.00

Screenshot 17. Donor Donation Inbox Interface.

- A. Name of agencies - This is a dropdown field that allows the donor to select a specific scholarship agency.
- B. Date of transaction - This is a dropdown field that enables the donor to select a specific month.

18. Student List

As shown in Screenshot 18, this interface displays the list of students under the selected scholarship agency. The list of students is presented in a tabular format, showing their academic information. Above the table, a school selection dropdown and a program search input field are provided. The school selection dropdown allows the donor to choose a specific school, filtering the list to display only students currently enrolled in the selected school.

The screenshot shows a web interface for viewing scholars. At the top, there is a search form with a 'School:' dropdown menu (labeled A) currently set to 'All', a 'Program:' search input field (labeled B), a 'Filter' button (labeled C), and a 'Return' button (labeled D). Below the search form is a table with three columns: 'Scholar Name', 'School', and 'Program of Study'. The table lists seven students, all from the University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R), with various programs of study.

Scholar Name	School	Program of Study
Adrian Magallanes	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Zachary Guzon	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Ern Jan	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Karen Kaye Alfonso	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	BS Computer Science
Wrenz Bancolo	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing
Von Andrei Awacay	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Dorothy Abanalo	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing

Screenshot 18. View Scholars Interface.

- A. School Selection – This is a drop-down menu that allows the donor to select a specific school where the students are currently enrolled.
- B. Search Program – This is a search input field that enables the donor to search and filter students based on their program of study.
- C. Filter – This button submits the selected criteria from the school drop-down menu and the program search field.
- D. Return – This button redirects the donor back to the previous page.

19. Scholarship Agency Registration

As shown in Screenshot 19, the Scholarship Agency Registration interface enables organizations to create a scholarship agency account by entering basic information such as agency name, contact number, email address, and password. The process is simple and user-friendly, guiding agencies through the required steps. Once submitted, the registration request is sent to the administrator for validation and approval before full system access is granted.

The screenshot shows a registration form with the following elements:

- Name of Scholarship Agency** (input field) with arrow **A** pointing to it.
- Contact** (input field) with arrow **B** pointing to it.
- Email** (input field) with arrow **C** pointing to it.
- Password** (input field) with arrow **D** pointing to it.
- Confirm Password** (input field) with arrow **E** pointing to it.
- Continue** (button) with arrow **F** pointing to it.
- Already have an Account? Login** (link) with arrow **G** pointing to it.

Screenshot 19. Scholarship Agency Registration Interface.

- A. Name – A text field where scholarship agencies enter their complete agency name for account registration.
- B. Contact – A text field where scholarship agency provides their active contact number for communication purposes.
- C. Email – A text field where scholarship agency input a valid email address to be used as their login credential and for account verification.
- D. Password – A text field where donors create a secure password for their account.
- E. Confirm Password – A text field where users re-enter their password to prevent errors.
- F. Continue - A button that submits the entered information and proceeds to the next step of the registration process.
- G. Already Have an Account – A link that redirects users back to the sign-in page if they already have an existing account.

20. Email Verification

As shown in Screenshot 20, the Email Verification interface allows users to confirm their account by entering a verification code sent to their registered email address. The process is simple and user friendly, guiding users to input the correct code to verify their identity. Once the code is submitted and validated by the system, the user is granted full access to all application features.

Screenshot 20. Email Verification Code.

A. Email Verification – A button that verifies the entered email address.

21. Scholarship Agency Navigation Bar

As shown in Screenshot 21, this interface serves as the primary dashboard for the scholarship agency, acting as the central hub for managing all activities within the application. It allows the scholarship agency to view, update, and edit profile information, ensuring that all account details remain accurate and up to date. The navigation panel provides access to key features such as Post, Profile, Criteria, Reports, Inbox, Donation History, and Calculation, enabling efficient movement between different sections of the system. In addition, the dashboard displays notifications, pending tasks, and recent activities, allowing the scholarship agency to monitor operations and respond to important updates promptly. The interface also provides quick access to financial records, student applications, and performance metrics, helping users manage responsibilities effectively.

Screenshot 21. Scholarship Agency Navigation Bar Interface.

- A. Post – A navigation option that allows users to create announcements, updates, or messages visible to relevant parties.
- B. Profile – A navigation option that allows users to view and manage their personal and academic account information.
- C. Criteria – A section where users view the eligibility or selection standards for scholarships or programs.
- D. Reports – A section where users view the summaries and analytics of activities, donations, or scholarship distribution.
- E. Inbox – A messaging feature that allows users to receive updates, notifications, and messages within the application.
- F. Donation History – A section where the records of all past donations, including amounts, dates, and recipients.

- G. Calculation – A section where the calculate scholarship distribution, allocate donations, and analyze related numerical data.
- H. Upload Photo – A file upload option that allows users to change their profile picture.
- I. Save – A button used to save and apply any changes made to forms, profiles, or entries.
- J. Edit Profile – A button that enables users to modify their personal information and update profile details.
- K. Upload Certificate – A file upload option that allows users to submit academic or achievement certificates.
- L. View Scholars – A dropdown field where users view list of scholars filtered by school via a drop-down menu.
- M. View Files – A section that provides access to uploaded documents, certificates, or reports.

22. Scholarship Matching Form

As shown in Screenshot 22, this feature allows the scholarship agency to match students to scholarships. The matching is based on the criteria previously set, including Location, Minimum Average Requirement, Supported Institutions, Tuition Coverage, Deadline of Application, and Coverage Type. These criteria ensure that only eligible students are paired with the appropriate scholarships. The interface gives a clear view of candidates, making efficient selection.

Screenshot 22. Scholarship Matching Form.

- A. Location – Specifies the geographic area where eligible applicants must reside or study.
- B. Minimum Average Requirement – A dropdown field that indicates the required minimum academic average or GPA for applicants.
- C. Supported Institutions - This field indicates the types of educational institutions supported by the application, including both public and private schools.
- D. Tuition Coverage – A dropdown field that defines the portion or percentage of tuition fees covered by the scholarship.
- E. Deadline of Application – A date selector that state the final date for submitting scholarship applications.

- F. Coverage Type – A dropdown field that describes the type of financial support provided.
- G. Set Criteria – A button that allows the scholarship provider to define additional eligibility requirements.
- H. Post a Scholarship – A button used to confirm and publish the scholarship listing based on the defined criteria.

23. Scholarship Posting Form

As shown in Screenshot 23, the application provides an interface for the scholarship agency to manage and organize scholarship information efficiently and systematically. The agency inputs detailed information about the scholarship benefits, including tuition coverage, allowances, and other inclusions, to ensure that students fully understand the support available and the scope of the scholarship. The interface also allows the agency to define eligibility requirements, application prerequisites, and the complete application process, guiding students through each step and reducing the likelihood of errors or incomplete submissions. Additional fields are provided for submission deadlines and announcement of results, helping applicants plan, prepare, and track their application progress effectively. The form is designed to be clear, intuitive, and user friendly, reducing confusion and ensuring that all relevant information is communicated in an organized manner.

Set Information About the Scholarship

Set Scholarship Benefits	Set Eligibility Requirement
<p>Enter Tuition Coverage</p> <p>35000.00 above <input type="button" value="v"/> A</p> <p>Scholarship Inclusion</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Monthly Living Allowance <input type="checkbox"/> Book and Educational Materials Allowance <input type="checkbox"/> One-Time Laptop or Gadget Grant B <input type="checkbox"/> Internet and Communication Support <input type="checkbox"/> Thesis or Research Grant <input type="checkbox"/> Internship or Mentorship Opportunities <input type="checkbox"/> Exclusive Training and Workshops <input type="checkbox"/> Health and Wellness Support <input type="checkbox"/> Employment Assistance After Graduation </p> <p>Other: <input type="text"/></p>	<p>Degree Preference Related to</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Science, Technology and Mathematics F <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Arts and Humanities <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and Forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Business, Hospitality and Finance </p> <p>Other: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Minimum Average Requirement</p> <p>75% - 80% <input type="button" value="v"/> G</p>
Set Application Requirement	Set Application Process
<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Certified True Copy of Grades or Transcript of Records <input type="checkbox"/> Certificate of Enrollment or Admission <input type="checkbox"/> Copy of Valid School ID <input type="checkbox"/> Income Tax Return (ITR) of parents/guardian <input type="checkbox"/> Certificate of Indigency from Barangay or Municipality C <input type="checkbox"/> Latest Payslip of Parents/Guardian <input type="checkbox"/> Certificate of Non-Filing of Income Tax <input type="checkbox"/> Birth Certificate <input type="checkbox"/> Parent's or Guardian's Valid ID <input type="checkbox"/> Medical Certificate <input type="checkbox"/> Barangay Clearance or Good Moral Certificate </p> <p>Other: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Deadline of Submission</p> <p>dd/mm/yyyy <input type="button" value="v"/> D</p> <p>Announcement of Result</p> <p>dd/mm/yyyy <input type="button" value="v"/></p>	<p>Set the Application Process in order</p> <p>1 <input type="text" value="Enter process 1 here"/> <input type="button" value="x"/></p> <p><input type="button" value="+"/></p> <p>H</p>
<p><input type="button" value="Submit"/> E F</p> <p style="font-size: small;">Set a Matching Criteria? Click Here A</p>	

Screenshot 23. Scholarship Posting Interface.

- A. Tuition Coverage – A dropdown field where the scholarship agency specifies the tuition fees covered by the scholarship.
- B. Scholarship Inclusion – A field used to list additional benefits included in the scholarship, such as allowances or other forms of support.

- C. Set Application Requirement – A field where the agency defines the documents and qualifications required from applicants.
- D. Deadline of Submission – A date selector where the agency sets the final date for submitting scholarship applications.
- E. Announcement of Result – A date selector that indicates when the results of the scholarship application be released.
- F. Degree Preference – A field where the agency specifies preferred degree programs eligible for the scholarship.
- G. Minimum Average Requirement – A dropdown field where the agency sets the minimum academic average required for applicants.
- H. Set Application Process – A field that allows the agency outlines the steps applicants must follow during the application process.
- I. Submit – A button used to save and publish the scholarship information entered by the agency.
- J. Click here – A links that redirects the scholarship agency to the scholarship matching criteria.

24. Scholarship Agency Inbox

As shown in Screenshot 24, the Inbox interface allows scholarship agencies to efficiently manage scholarship applications and track received donations. The interface displays a list of pending applicants, providing options to view, review, and validate each application to ensure that all submitted information meets the scholarship requirements. In

In addition, the donations list presents detailed information for each contribution, including donor details, dates, payment methods, amounts, and uploaded receipts, giving agencies a clear and organized overview of financial support received. Action buttons within the interface enable agencies to acknowledge donations, mark them as processed, or delete records if necessary, helping maintain an accurate and up-to-date record of all transactions.

The screenshot displays two tables within a web interface. The top table, titled 'Applications', has columns for 'Student Name', 'Date Submitted', and 'Action'. It contains one entry for 'Adrian Magallanes' with a date of '2025-12-25 12:49:29' and a green eye icon in the 'Action' column, labeled 'A'. Below this is a 'Donations' table with columns: 'Donor Name', 'Date of Donation', 'Payment Method', 'Amount', 'Receipt', and 'Action'. It lists five donations from 'Libertad NGO' with various dates and amounts (P1415.00, P60000.00, P10000.00, P50000.00, P50000.00). Each row has an eye icon in the 'Receipt' column and a green thumbs-up and red 'X' icon in the 'Action' column. Callouts 'B', 'C', and 'D' point to the eye icon, the thumbs-up icon, and the 'X' icon respectively.

Student Name	Date Submitted	Action
Adrian Magallanes	2025-12-25 12:49:29	

Donor Name	Date of Donation	Payment Method	Amount	Receipt	Action
Libertad NGO	2025-11-15 15:08:21	gcash	P1415.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-10-31 07:50:58	gcash	P60000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-10-15 14:54:52	gcash	P10000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-08-24 07:37:06	gcash	P50000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-07-24 07:33:31	gcash	P50000.00		

Screenshot 24. Scholarship Agency Inbox Interface.

- A. View Applicant – A button that allows scholarship agencies to view applicant details and continue the application validation process.
- B. View receipt – A button that displays the uploaded transaction receipt for the selected donation.
- C. Acknowledge – A button used to confirm and acknowledge receipt of the donation.
- D. Delete – A button that removes the selected donation record from the system.

25. Calculation Method

As shown in Screenshot 25, the system provides multiple remittance calculation methods for scholarship distribution. These include Top 20 Percent, Top 30 Percent, Top 10, Top 20, and Divided Equally, each determining how donation amounts are allocated based on academic performance or equal sharing. The selected method automatically calculates and distributes the total donations according to the defined rules.

Calculation Method for AY 2025-2026 First Semester

Divide Equally

Approve for Disbursement

Calculation for Distribution

Total Amount of Donations: ₱150000
Total no. of Scholars: 17
Amount per Scholar: ₱8,23.53

Scholar	Amount
Adrian Magallanes	₱8,23.53
Zachary Guzon	₱8,23.53
Ern Jan	₱8,23.53
Karen Kaye Alfonso	₱8,23.53
Wrenz Bancalo	₱8,23.53
Van Andrei Awaaooy	₱8,23.53
Dorothy Abanalo	₱8,23.53
Niel Yuri Adolfo	₱8,23.53
Antonio Camacho	₱8,23.53
Jeptha Osorio	₱8,23.53

Screenshot 25. Calculation Method Interface.

- A. Selection of Calculation – Allows the scholarship agency to select the preferred calculation method for distributing donations, ensuring funds are allocated according to agency rules and student eligibility.
- B. Approve Distribution – Confirms and applies the selected calculation method, enabling the scholarship agency to proceed with accurate and organized fund distribution to students.

In summary, EduCash provides a comprehensive user guide that walks users through the various interfaces and functionalities of the application, ensuring that all stakeholders navigate the system with ease and confidence. The succeeding sections, including the student registration process, credential upload interface, donor and scholarship agency dashboards, donation workflow, and inbox management, highlight the core features and capabilities of the system, illustrating how each component contributes to a seamless user experience. With a strong emphasis on usability, security, and efficient information management, the application is designed to support students, donors, and scholarship agencies in a structured, organized, and reliable manner. Overall, EduCash aims to deliver an accessible, transparent, and trustworthy platform for managing scholarships and financial assistance, providing a comprehensive solution that addresses both administrative and user needs. The structured presentation of system interfaces reinforces clarity and consistency across different user roles, promoting ease of navigation, reducing operational errors, and enhancing the overall efficiency and effectiveness of system interactions. Clear workflows, well-defined processes, and comprehensive interface guidance further contribute to smooth coordination among stakeholders, ensuring that all scholarship activities are properly monitored and executed. Additionally, the integration of notifications, real-time updates, and centralized dashboards ensures that users are informed promptly of all relevant developments, allowing for timely decision-making and effective management of tasks. The platform also facilitates accurate tracking of donations, scholarship applications, and financial distributions, supporting transparency and accountability at every stage of the process.

APPENDIX A

Mutual Agreement Form for Co-Authorship.
(Adopted from Philippine Association of Institutions for Research (PAIR), Inc.)

WE, the researcher, and research adviser/consultant, have worked together in a capstone project from August 2024 to May 2025.

WE have used various forms of contact during the capstone project work such as Microsoft Teams, Facebook and other means of communication.

WE agree that :

- the academic partnership leads to publication of the manuscript with the research consultant as the author and the researcher, the primary author.
- the paper be presented in public forum by the researcher if available at such an opportunity or by the research adviser/consultant if the researcher is no longer around.
- only the name of the oral presenter shall be submitted to the Conference organizer.

WE agree to dress formally and prepare adequately for the formal oral presentation in both the oral defense panel and the public presentations.

Signed this 27th of July in the year of our Lord 2025 in Bacolod City, Philippines.

VON ANDREI G. AWACAY
Researcher

CHRISTINE JOY S. DORIAS
Technical Consultant

JHON PATRICK B. PEREZ
Researcher

ELMER T. HARO, Ph.D.
Course Adviser

JONH LORENCE G. REYES
Researcher

MARK ANGELO C. NAVARRO
Witness

APPENDIX B

EduCash Concept Paper.

Capstone Project Concept Title	EduCash		
Concept Author and Collaborator(s)	Jhon Patrick B. Perez	Von Andrei G. Awacay	Jonh Lorence G. Reyes
	Main Author	Collaborator #1	Collaborator #2
Rationale of the Capstone Project Concept			
<p>EduCash is an online system carefully designed to respond to the financial challenges of less privileged but worthy college students in Bacolod City in response to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality Education. It overcomes systemic barriers in access to higher education by providing connections between students and donors, NGOs, and private individuals who are willing to give out finances. Its focus is on ensuring equity in access to education, marking a commitment toward fostering academic excellence and reducing economic constraints. Facilitating a smooth interface for matching scholarships, making financial transactions, and interactions between donors and students, EduCash acts as a revolutionary tool empowering students to achieve their academic dreams while promoting participation by the community in education.</p>			
Main Features and Functionalities			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Document Verification – Upon registration, users are required to submit valid documents. These documents are verified using this feature to prevent fraudulent data in the platform. 2. Scholarship Match – This feature allows students to connect to scholarship agency, providing them efficient inquiry by matching their credentials to whatever scholarship agency they are suitable/ 3. Donor portal – this feature provides a personalized space for donors where they track and send donations to scholarship agencies. 4. Data Analytics - This data analytics feature displayed in a dashboard consists of the data such as total amount of donations gathered, total number of applicants, total number of NGO donors, which are represented in a bar graph, and a pie chart of the percentage of the individual and anonymous donors. This feature serve as a significant element for evaluating the performance of the platform. Generation of comprehensive reports to provide users a valuable awareness of the operation and impact of the platform. Specifically, the platform provides an analyzation and display key metrics that be discussed further in this section of the paper. 5. Allowance Distribution - In this feature, the students claim financial aid calculated by the platform through payment gateways integrated in the platform. The distribution be scheduled on a specific month each semester and each time before the distribution, students must submit their academic performance. Students must maintain their academic performance as for the eligibility criteria to avoid being dropped as a recipient of the platform. Reaching below the criteria result to drop automatically from the platform. 			
Project Usability / Benefit Justification			
<p>This platform is useful for both students, and scholarship agencies. Using this platform, scholarship agencies cater to students who really deserves to be granted with financial support since students that are catered by the platform are only those who excel in their academic performance. The platform also motivates the students to be committed in their education since the platform has a retention policy.</p>			
Relevance to the Theme			
EduCash aligns with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by addressing Goal 4 (Quality Education)			
Technology Deployment			
<p>Frontend: HTML/, CSS, BOOTSTRAP, JavaScript. Backend: MySQL, Python, Django. Search Engine: Google</p>			
Anticipated Challenges			
<p>One major challenge for the project team possibly be the donor and agency engagement. without these actors, the platform does not do what it is programmed for since the platform relies on donors as it is a fundraising platform.</p>			

APPENDIX C

PERT Table.

Act Codes	Activity	Predecessor	Duration (Weeks)
A	Project Conceptualization	None	1
B	Identify Project Requirements	A	1
C	Identify and Reviewing of Related Systems	B	3
D	Identify Software and Hardware Requirements	C	1
E	Identify System Features	D	3
F	Design Prototyping	E	3
G	Frontend Development	F	16
H	Backend Development	F	21
I	Testing and debugging	H	2
J	Final Documentation	I	1

APPENDIX D

PERT Diagram.

APPENDIX E

Gantt Chart.

APPENDIX F

Project Cost.

PROJECT COST	YEARLY COST	SERVICE
Internet	Php 15,588.00	PLDT WIFI
Prototype	Php P4,265.00	Canva/Figma
Content	Php 1,387.00	Grammarly
TOTAL SYSTEM COST	Php 21,240.00	
System Support and Maintenance	Php 2,000.00	Cloud Services
Tools	Php 1,500.00	APIs Services
OPERATION AND MAINTENANCE COST	Php 3,500.00	

APPENDIX G

Cost Benefit Analysis.

	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Total System Cost	₱21,240.00					
Operation and Maintenance Cost	₱0.00	₱3,500.00	₱3,850.00	₱4,235.00	₱4,658.50	₱5,124.35
Discount Factor (12%)	1.00	0.87	0.80	0.71	0.64	0.57
Time Adjusted Cost	₱21,240.00	₱3,045.00	₱3,080.00	₱3,006.85	₱2,981.44	₱2,920.88
Cumulative Time Adjusted Cost	₱21,240.00	₱24,285.00	₱27,365.00	₱30,371.85	₱33,353.29	₱36,274.17
Benefits derived from operation of New System	₱0.00	₱50,000.00	₱55,000.00	₱60,500.00	₱66,550.00	₱73,205.00
Discount Factor (12%)	1.00	0.87	0.80	0.71	0.64	0.57
Time Adjusted Benefits	₱0.00	₱43,500.00	₱44,000.00	₱42,955.00	₱42,592.00	₱41,726.85
Cumulative Time Adjusted Benefits	₱0.00	₱43,500.00	₱87,500.00	₱130,455.00	₱173,047.00	₱214,773.85
Cumulative Time Adjusted Cost + Benefits	₱21,240.00	₱19,215.00	₱60,135.00	₱100,083.15	₱139,693.71	₱178,499.68

Return of Investments (ROI)	491.52%
Net Present Value (NPV)	Php 178,499.68
Payback Period	0.49 years

APPENDIX H

Product Logo.

The EduCash logo symbolizes empowering individuals through education and financial support for their educational journeys. The person with graduation cap represents the pursuit of knowledge, wisdom, and aspiring students for academic success and to move forward seeking greater success. The green in "Cash" symbolizes growth and financial wellbeing, indicating opportunities. The typeface combines the words "Edu" which is short for education and "Cash" which is for financial support emphasizing the linking of knowledge with funds. The broken line circle with arrow symbolizes the distribution of the funds. The green cash icon symbolizes the effectiveness of the distribution of funding meeting the educational requirements of students.

APPENDIX I

Team Logo.

The "Triple Transcendence" symbolizes beyond limits through the combined strength of three interconnected forces. The typography of "Triple Transcendence" serves as the anchor of the logo, ensuring a sturdy visual identity. The logo visually represents unity, growth, and progress through its design elements. The three human Figures represent three of us indicating teamwork, self-determination, and stability. The upward motion of the Figure highlights growth and collective success of the team. The three arches on the top signify movement and progress. The Figures and arches work together to convey harmony, forward motion, and the idea of surpassing limits.

APPENDIX J

Ethical Table.

Tool Used	Purpose	Prompt / Activity	Results	References
ChatGPT-5	To assist in technical writing and documentation.	Generate and expand paragraphs. Provide comprehensive explanations of system processes and functional features.	Improved clarity, formal tone of documentation while maintaining developer authored content.	Chapters 1–7 Documentation.
Tesseract OCR	Optical Character Recognition (OCR) for reading documents.	Converts scanned grade reports, certificates, and identification documents into digital text for verification.	Improved efficiency and accuracy of document pre-verification processes.	Application Document Verification.
PayPal API	To allow local digital wallet donations	Handle payments and transaction confirmations through PayPal secure gateway.	Allowed accessible and secure donations.	Online Payment Gateways.
GCash API	To allow local digital wallet donations	Process GCash payments initiated by donors.	Allowed accessible and secure donations.	Online Payment Gateways.
Maya API	To allow local digital wallet donations	Handle Maya-based transactions and confirmations.	Allowed accessible and secure donations.	Online Payment Gateways.
PHPMailer (SMTP Email Service)	Send donation receipts, account verifications, and system notifications	Send donation receipts, account verifications, and system notifications.	Provided reliable email communication.	Email Notification Services.

APPENDIX K

Minutes of Capstone Project Proposal Defense.

December 16, 2025| 2:30PM – 4:00PM

College of Information Technology.

University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

Project Proposal Title	EduCash
Group Members	Von Andrei G. Awacay Jhon Patrick B. Perez Jonh Lorence G. Reyes
Panel Members	Joshua E. Dela Cruz Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D. Kyron Edyzon N. Sol
Interpellators	Jules Alfonz Pecaoco Fhilam Joy Villaflor

1. The conference started exactly at 2:30AM with a prayer led by Jhon Patrick B. Perez.
2. The group members were introduced by Jonh Lorence G. Reyes.
3. The oral presentation was delivered by Jonh Lorence G. Reyes.
4. After The presentation, the following are the suggestions and recommendations of the panel members and the interpellators.

Chapter/Section	Recommendations/ Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken	Proof
INTRODUCTION				
SYSTEM SPECIFICATIONS				
APPENDICES	Clearly state the information about the calculation of money to the students.	Joshua E. Dela Cruz	Composed a new section in the Design Implementation constraints.	Table 4. (page 25)

SYSTEM FEATURES	<p>Allow scholarship agencies to post announcements that are viewable in the interface of the students, informing them of specific procedures to apply for a scholarship.</p> <p>Construct clearly how the calculation functions.</p>		<p>Composed a subsection for 2.1.2 Scholarship Match.</p> <p>Composed a new section in the Design Implementation Constraints.</p>	<p>2.1.2.1 Postings. (Page 17)</p> <p>2.3.2 Calculation for Distribution. (Page 25)</p>
SYSTEM FEATURES/ PROTOTYPES	Improve the design of the UI.	<p>Joshua E. Dela Cruz</p> <p>Jules Alfonz Pecaoco</p> <p>Kyrond Edyzon Sol</p>	Revised the prototype and added some more functionality.	CHAPTER IV (Page 54)
	Provide more data representation in the data analytics feature.	Kyrond Edyzon Sol.	Added a bar graph representation.	Figure 28. (Page 80)
PROJECT MANAGEMENT				
GLOSSARY				
APPENDICES	In the logo, add more elements that highlight other functions such as the distribution of money.	Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.	Provided more elements that features other functionality.	APPENDIX H (Page 170)

REFERENCES				
CURRICULUM VITAE				

6. After deliberation of interpellators and panel members, the proposal is considered accepted with minor revisions.
7. The conference ended exactly at 3:36PM.

Transcribed by : Von Andrei G. Awacay

Noted by : Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.

APPENDIX L

Minutes of Capstone Project Final Defense.

May 27, 2025 | 10:30AM – 12:00PM

College of Information Technology.

University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

Project Proposal Title	EduCash
Group Members	Von Andrei G. Awacay Jhon Patrick B. Perez Jonh Lorence G. Reyes
Panel Members	Joshua E. Dela Cruz Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D. Reinhardt Firmeza
Interpellators	Jules Alfonz Pecaoco Andrew Batuigas

1. The conference started exactly at 10:30AM with a prayer led by Von Andrei G. Awacay
2. The group members were introduced by Jonh Lorence G. Reyes.
3. The oral presentation was delivered by Jonh Lorence G. Reyes.
4. After The presentation, the following are the suggestions and recommendations of the panel members and the interpellators.

Chapter/Section	Recommendations/ Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken	Proof
INTRODUCTION				
SYSTEM SPECIFICATIONS				
APPENDICES	Revision of the product logo.	Reinhardt Firmeza	Removed some elements that are redundant.	APPENDIX H (Page 170)
SYSTEM FEATURES	Provide admin user to monitor the scholarship agencies.	Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.	Added admin to monitor and to check the scholarship agencies are	Figure 29 (Page 81)

	<p>Consolidate some parts of the UI to distinguish account types.</p> <p>Provide email verification upon registration.</p>	Reinhardt Firmeza	<p>certified and legit.</p> <p>Added a color-coded interface for each account type.</p> <p>Composed an email verification before the user can login.</p>	<p>Table 5. (Page 27)</p> <p>Screenshot 20. (Page 153)</p>
	<p>Provide students a way to inform to the agencies that they receive the remittance.</p> <p>Allow agencies to check the documents once they accepted the application.</p> <p>Some currency values are not separated by comma.</p> <p>Allow the donors to filter the donation history based on agencies.</p>	Joshua E. Dela Cruz	<p>Added a feature where students are able to acknowledge the remittance.</p> <p>Added a functionality to check the documents of the students.</p> <p>Added decimals and comma in the currency values.</p> <p>Provided a dropdown feature to filter the agencies.</p>	<p>Figure 12. (Page 64)</p> <p>Figure 23. (Page 75)</p> <p>Figure 20 (Page 72)</p> <p>Figure 20 (Page 72)</p>

	Let the donor know who the students in the scholarship agencies.	Jules Alfonz Pecaoco	Added a view function that view the scholars in the agencies.	Figure 21. (Page 73)
	Allow the system to check for the legitimacy of the scholarship agencies.	Andrew Batuigas	Added an admin user to monitor the scholarship agencies.	Figure 29. (Page 81)

6. After deliberation of interpellators and panel members, the proposal is considered accepted with minor revisions.
7. The conference ended exactly at 12:00PM.

Transcribed by : Von Andrei G. Awacay

Noted by : Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.

APPENDIX M

Product Packaging.

The EduCash product packaging is designed in the form of a graduation cap to represent academic achievement and student success. The central display emphasizes the system as a core platform for managing financial assistance and scholarship processes. The overall design highlights the key features of EduCash, including system functions, requirements, and supporting software tools, which are presented on dedicated panels.

APPENDIX N

Product Poster.

EduCash
Your Bridge to a Brighter Academic Future

It is a web-based application that links donors and scholarship agencies with financially challenged yet deserving college students in Bacolod City. It offers a transparent platform for donations, guarantees proper fund distribution, and connects students with scholarship opportunities, enabling them to pursue their education without financial obstacles.

It matches qualified students with scholarship agencies based on set academic and financial criteria.

SYSTEM FEATURES

- DATA ANALYTICS**: It provides reports and visual insights on donations, donors, and applicants to track system performance.
- SCHOLARSHIP MATCHING**: It matches qualified students with scholarship agencies based on set academic and financial criteria.
- DOCUMENT VERIFICATION**: It validates uploaded student documents to ensure authenticity and prevent fraudulent applications.
- ALLOWANCE CALCULATION**: It calculates how student allowances are distributed, using a one-time selection of the preferred calculation method.
- DONOR PORTAL**: It allows donors to contribute funds securely through multiple payment gateways and receive transaction receipts.

TECHNOLOGIES: HTML, PHP, MySQL

Contact us : educash@gmail.com
Visit us : educash.com

DEVELOPER BY:
Von Andrei Awacay
Ehon Paricles Parez
Josh Lorenzo Reyes

APPENDIX O

Integrity Score Computation.

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Only users are able to alter their personal information.	Resolved
When editing user information, users must provide their password for confirmation.	Not Resolved
Administrators are able to alter user information	Not Resolved
When trying to access the “forgot password” feature, an email confirmation is sent to the users.	Resolved
$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $I = \frac{2}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	50%

Financial Transactions	
Requirements	Status
Only scholarship agencies are able to see the total amount that they received	Resolved
Donations are recorded	Resolved
Student receives the donation	Resolved
Every donation has system generated receipt	Not Resolved
Receipts are sent to the recipients for acknowledgement	Resolved
Total amount for each scholarship agencies is updated	Resolved
$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $I = \frac{5}{6} \times 100$	
Mean Score	50%

APPENDIX P

Confidentiality Score Computation.

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Users must register an account	Resolved
The users must be verified before they are able to access the features	Resolved
Passwords are hashed in the database	Not Resolved
Email verifications are only sent to email provided	Resolved
$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CF = \frac{3}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	75%

Financial Transactions	
Requirements	Status
System keeps the contact information of donors	Resolved
Donors are able to stay anonymous	Resolved
Receipts are not modifiable	Resolved
Receipts are only visible to donor and recipient	Resolved
Only donors are able to view their donation history	Resolved
Donors are not able to see the total amount of donation per agency	Resolved
$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CF = \frac{6}{6} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

APPENDIX Q

Authenticity Score Computation.

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Email and Username are found in the database	Resolved
Age restrictions	Not Resolved
Passwords match with the email provided	Resolved
Password complexity	Resolved
Password recovery	Not Resolved
Session Timeout	Resolved
Multiple devices logged in	Resolved
Multiple tabs logged in	Not Resolved
$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $AU = \frac{5}{8} \times 100$	
Mean Score	62.5%

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Donation amounts are saved in the database	Resolved
Amount restrictions	Not Resolved
Clarity of receipts	Resolved
Duplicate donations	Resolved
Amount extraction in receipts	Resolved
Confirmation	Not Resolved
$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $AU = \frac{4}{6} \times 100$	
Mean Score	66.7%

APPENDIX R

Completeness Score Computation.

Scholarship Matching and Postings	
Requirements	Status
Scholarship agencies are able to post deadlines	Complete
Match students based on the criteria set	Complete
Students are limited only to one scholarship	Not Complete
More than one matches are displayed for the students	Complete
Scholarship agencies are required to set criteria	Complete
Scholarship agencies set criteria only once	Not Complete
Scholarship agencies are notified about the matched student	Complete
Scholarship agencies are able to cross check the documents	Complete
$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CP = \frac{6}{8} \times 100$	
Mean Score	75%

Calculation	
Requirements	Status
Scholarship agencies are able to choose a method of calculation	Complete
Overview of the calculation method before approval	Complete
Donors are informed about the method of calculation of each agency	Complete
Students are informed in the calculation method before receiving the money	Not Complete
$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CP = \frac{3}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	75%

APPENDIX S

Correctness Score Computation.

Scholarship Matching and Postings	
Requirements	Status
Submit button for criteria form	Correct
Submit button for postings form	Correct
Apply button for students	Correct
Error messages	Correct
Success messages	Correct
$CR = \frac{\text{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CR = \frac{5}{5} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

Calculation	
Requirements	Status
Approve button for calculation dropdown	Correct
One calculation per period	Correct
Method of calculations	Correct
$CR = \frac{\text{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CR = \frac{3}{3} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

APPENDIX T

Consistency Score Computation.

Scholarship Matching and Postings	
Requirements	Status
Matches align with the criteria	Consistent
Students matched with scholarship agencies based on average required	Consistent
Procedures and guidelines are posted by scholarship agencies	Consistent
Users must be verified to use this feature	Consistent
$CS = \frac{\text{number of consistent functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CS = \frac{4}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

Calculation	
Requirements	Status
Students receive the amount based on the calculation	Consistent
The calculation scales on the amount and the number of students	Consistent
All students are able to receive in all methods of calculation	Not Consistent
$CS = \frac{\text{number of consistent functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CS = \frac{2}{3} \times 100$	
Mean Score	66.7%

APPENDIX U

Survey Result.

Criteria	Mean Score
Execution Efficiency	4.54
Code Simplicity	4.51
Communication Commonality	4.5
Security	4.5
Completeness	4.49
Data Commonality	4.48
Traceability	4.48
Expandability	4.46
Training	4.46
Controllability	4.45
Decomposability	4.45
Functional Simplicity	4.45
Instrumentation	4.44
Modularity	4.44
Self-Documentation	4.44
Auditability	4.43
Observability	4.42
Accuracy	4.41
Consistency and Understandability	4.41
Conciseness	4.39
Generality	4.38
Structural Simplicity	4.38
Operability	4.35
Software System Independence	4.35
Error Tolerance	4.34
Hardware Independence	4.29

APPENDIX V
Grammarly Results.

EduCash (Chapters 1 & 2)

by UNO-R Researcher

General metrics

44,571	6,272	347	25 min 5 sec	48 min 14 sec
characters	words	sentences	reading time	speaking time

Score

This text scores better than 95% of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

82	19	63
Issues left	Critical	Advanced

Plagiarism

This text hasn't been checked for plagiarism

EduCash (Chapters 3 & 4)

by UNO-R Researcher

General metrics

46,047	6,828	421	27 min 18 sec	52 min 31 sec
characters	words	sentences	reading time	speaking time

Score

This text scores better than 95% of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

100	18	82
Issues left	Critical	Advanced

Plagiarism

This text hasn't been checked for plagiarism

EduCash (Chapters 5 & 6)

by UNO-R Researcher

General metrics

35,878	4,871	256	19 min 29 sec	37 min 28 sec
characters	words	sentences	reading time	speaking time

Score

95

This text scores better than 95% of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

62	8	54
Issues left	Critical	Advanced

Plagiarism

This text hasn't been checked for plagiarism

EduCash (Chapter 7 & User's Manual)

by UNO-R Researcher

General metrics

11,182	1,438	57	5 min 45 sec	11 min 3 sec
characters	words	sentences	reading time	speaking time

Score

96

This text scores better than 96% of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

15	8	7
Issues left	Critical	Advanced

Plagiarism

This text hasn't been checked for plagiarism

APPENDIX W

Turnitin Results.

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